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Report on sustainability indicators for the monitoring system based on Life Cycle Assessment

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Partners short names

TUB	Technische Universitat Berlin
UNITELMA	Università degli studi Unitelma di Roma
UNI	Ente Italiano di Normazione
AUA	Geoniko Panepistimion Athinon
USC	Universidade de Santiago de Compostela
APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
NOVA	Institut for politische und Okologische Innovation GMBH
BB	Better Biomass
BAM	Bundesanstalt fuer Materialforschung und Pruefung
RSB	Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials Association
ISEAL	Iseal Alliance

Acronyms

SCS	Sustainable Certification Schemes
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
S-LCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
TEA	Techno-economic Analysis
WP	Work package
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
GHG	Greenhouse gas
NGOs	Non-governmental organizations
iLUC	Indirect land use change
ILCD	International Life Cycle Data System
PEF	Product Environmental Footprint
SHDB	Social Hotspot Database
PSILCA	Product Social Impact Life Cycle Assessment

Term	Definition
Bio-based products	Products wholly or partly derived from biomass, such as plants, trees or animals (the biomass can have undergone physical, chemical or biological treatment) (BS EN 16751, 2016).
Cascading use	Cascading use is the efficient utilization of resources by using residues and recycled materials for material use to extend total biomass availability within a given system. From a technical perspective the cascading use of wood takes place when wood is processed into a product and this product is used at least once more either for material or energy purposes (Vis et al., 2016).
Certification schemes	The system of rules, procedures and management for carrying out certification, including the standards against which it is being certified (Dankers, 2003).
Characterization factor	Factor derived from a characterization model which is applied to convert an assigned life cycle inventory analysis result to the common unit of the category indicator (ISO 14040, 2006).
Characterization model	Characterization model is a mathematical model that links and quantifies the potential contribution of elementary flows to a specific impact with the use of characterization factors (Adapted from Alejandro et al., 2022).
Environmental Life Cycle Assessment (E-LCA)	Environmental Life Cycle Assessment (E-LCA) is a methodology for assessing environmental impacts associated with all the stages of the life cycle of a product, service or organization (UNEP Life Cycle Initiative and Social LC Alliance, 2020).
Feedstock	Primary or secondary material that is used to produce a product (ISO 14040, 2006).
Impact category	Class representing environmental issues of concern to which life cycle inventory analysis results may be assigned (ISO 14040, 2006).
Indicator	A quantitative, qualitative or binary variable that can be measured or described to assess an aspect of a defined criterion (BS EN 16751, 2016).
Indirect land use change (iLUC)	When feedstock is produced on existing agricultural land, the demand for food and feed crops remains, and may lead to someone producing more food and feed somewhere else (Adapted from European Commission, 2012).

Term	Definition
Indirect land use change (iLUC) emissions	The amount of CO ₂ emissions are released into the atmosphere due to indirect land use change (European Commission, 2012).
Label	A certification label is a label or symbol indicating that compliance with standards has been verified. While the certificate is a form of communication between seller and buyer, the label is a form of communication with the end consumer (Dankers, 2003).
Life cycle	All consecutive and/or interlinked stages, including research and development to be carried out, production, trading and its conditions, transport, use and maintenance, throughout the existence of the product or the works or the provision of the service, from raw material acquisition or generation of resources to disposal, clearance and end of service or utilization (Parliament et al., 2018).
Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)	The compilation and evaluation of the inputs, outputs and potential environmental impacts of a product system throughout its life cycle (ISO 14040, 2006).
Life Cycle Costing (LCC)	Life-cycle costing is an award criterion which covers parts or all of the following costs over the life cycle of a product, service or works (Parliament et al., 2018).
Monitoring and evaluation system	An ongoing process through which an organization draws conclusions about its contribution to intended outcomes and impacts. A monitoring and evaluation system consists of a set of interconnected functions, processes and activities, including systematic collection of monitoring data on specified indicators and the implementation of outcome and impact evaluations (Alliance for Water Stewardship (AWS), 2022).
Non-renewable resources	Minerals, oil, gas and coal. Their use as material and energy sources leads to depletion of the Earth's reserves and are characterized that they do not renew in human relevant periods (European Environment Agency, 2023).
Qualitative data	Data describing the attributes or properties that an object possesses. The properties are categorized into classes that may be assigned numeric values. However, there is no significance to the data values themselves, they simply represent attributes of the object concerned (Marine Stewardship Council, 2023).
Quantitative data	Data expressing a certain quantity, amount or range. Usually, there are measurement units associated with the data (Marine Stewardship Council, 2023).

Term	Definition
Renewable resources	Renewable resources are resources derived from natural sources that are replenished at a higher rate than they are consumed. Sunlight and wind, for example, are such sources that are constantly being replenished (Adapted from United Nations, 2023).
Secondary raw materials	Secondary raw materials are recycled materials that can be used in manufacturing processes instead of or alongside virgin raw materials (European Parliament, 2023).
S-LCA	A social and socio-economic Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) is a social impact (and potential impact) assessment technique that aims to assess the social and socio-economic aspects of products and their potential positive and negative impacts along their life cycle encompassing extraction and processing of raw materials; manufacturing; distribution; use; re-use; maintenance; recycling; and final disposal (UNEP Life Cycle Initiative and Social LC Alliance, 2020).
Stakeholder	Individual or group that has an interest in any activities or decisions of an organization (UNEP Life Cycle Initiative and Social LC Alliance, 2020).
Substitution effect	It represents the potential reduction of GHG emissions coming from the marginal replacement of a non-wood based functional equivalent product. For example, the reduction of GHG emissions when employing wood for construction instead of concrete (Brunet-Navarro et al., 2021; Swedish University of Agricultural Science, 2023).
System boundary	Set of criteria specifying which unit processes are part of a product system (ISO 14040, 2006).
Techno-economic analysis (TEA)	Methodological approach to analyze the technical and economic performance of a process, product, or product system (Mahmud et al., 2021b).
Value chain	The entire sequence of activities or parties that provide or receive value in the form of products or services (e.g., suppliers, outsources workers, contractors, investors, R&D, customers, consumers, members) (ISO14001 CD2, 2013).

Executive Summary

The primary objective of the STAR4BBS project is to improve the effectiveness of sustainability certification schemes and labels in supporting a sustainable bio-based economy. This will be accomplished through the development of a new monitoring system that evaluates the robustness, performance and impact of certification schemes and labels. In this regard, the establishment of a comprehensive set of sustainability indicators is an essential component of the monitoring system. Specifically, this report focuses on the identification and provision of sustainability indicators under the life cycle perspective with a twofold objective: i) to incorporate them into the new established monitoring system, and ii) to apply them in the evaluation of the sustainability performance of selected value chains, which will be conducted in future activities of the project.

As a first step, a classification was developed to map and categorize the wide range of sustainability issues. Furthermore, an analysis of scientific and grey literature was conducted to identify the available LCA indicators under the three pillars of sustainability (environmental, economic and social). All data, for each of the aforementioned pillars, were collected in a separate database, which included parameters such as the characterization model, unit of measurement, life cycle stages, and sectors. As a second step, the list of identified indicators was refined to include only those considered as relevant, operational, and the most robust and reliable; in this process, potential overlaps were also checked.

In total, 44, 22, and 571 LCA indicators were identified in the environmental, economic, and social pillars, respectively, which were further reduced to 16, 8, and 101 indicators according to a predefined set of criteria (e.g., robustness, operability). Although most of the indicators were found to be applicable to all life cycle stages and sectors of the bioeconomy, there were some, especially in the social dimension, that were limited to certain stages and/or sectors. In addition, the social pillar was the only one to report a combination of qualitative and quantitative indicators, while for the environmental and economic pillars all indicators were quantifiable.

1 Introduction

The STAR4BBS project aims to maximize the potential of Sustainability Certification Schemes (SCS) and labels in supporting a successful transition to a sustainable bio-based economy by creating a monitoring system that evaluates the effectiveness and reliability of schemes applicable to biological feedstocks and bio-based materials and products.

Sustainability indicators are an essential part of the monitoring system (referred to as *content level*, see *Box 1 of Deliverable 1.4 of STAR4BBS – www.star4bbs.eu*), as they enable the assessment of the sustainability coverage of SCS and their level of stringency. Depending on whether the sustainability indicators follow the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology or not, the project distinguishes between two broad types of indicators: LCA indicators and non-LCA indicators. While the former is the focus of this report (D 3.1 “Report on sustainability indicators for the monitoring system based on Life Cycle Assessment”), the latter will be addressed in the next deliverable (D 3.2 “Report on additional indicators of monitoring system”).

The Life Cycle Assessment methodology is defined by ISO standard 14040 (2006) as a “compilation and evaluation of the inputs, outputs and the potential environmental impact of a product system throughout its life cycle”, i.e., from the extraction of raw materials, manufacturing, distribution, use and end of life. The methodology consists of four main steps: 1) *goal and scope definition*, 2) *life cycle inventory*, 3) *life cycle impact assessment* and 4) *interpretation*. During the life cycle impact assessment phase, the inventoried flows (e.g., emissions, raw materials used) are translated into environmental impacts by assigning impact factors (Figure 1).

The LCA methodology is recognized by the European Commission as the foremost framework for evaluating the potential environmental impacts of products (European Commission, 2023a, 2023b). It allows the simultaneous quantitative measurement of multiple environmental indicators over the entire life cycle, facilitating the identification of trade-offs and potential opportunities for improvement. However, social and economic aspects must also be taken into account in order to achieve sustainability. In this regard, the Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) and Life Cycle Costing (LCC) focus on assessing the social and economic impacts, respectively, following the four steps of the LCA framework¹ (Sala et al., 2015). Given its proven strength in sustainability assessment (European Commission, 2023a, 2023b), the LCA methodology, encompassing environmental, social and economic aspects, has been selected as the tool for evaluating the costs and benefits of certifying bio-based value chains. Furthermore, it stands out as one of the recommended methodologies within the monitoring system. Accordingly, this report has a twofold objective: firstly, to establish a set of LCA indicators for conducting a sustainability assessment of the value chains in future work of the project. Secondly, the identified LCA indicators could potentially be integrated into the content level of the monitoring system. The

¹ Life cycle sustainability assessment (LCSA) integrates the evaluation of environmental, social and economic negative impacts and benefits of products and services across their life cycle (UNEP-SETAC Life Cycle Initiative, 2023).

approach to achieving these goals involves developing a classification system of different areas of sustainability concern, a desk analysis of available LCA indicators, and ultimately selecting the most suitable LCA indicators for evaluating the case studies.

Figure 1. Phases of the Life Cycle Inventory and the Environmental Impact Assessment through examples of substances, impact categories and indicators.

The report is structured as follows: **section 2** outlines the methodology used for developing the sustainability areas classification, as well as for identifying and selecting LCA indicators. In **section 3** the established classification is described. Moving to **section 4**, the LCA indicators related to the environmental, social, and economic dimensions are presented. Lastly, **section 5** provides a summary of the key findings and insights.

2 Methodology

This section describes the various steps taken to define the final set of LCA indicators, starting with the development of the classification (**section 2.1**), and continuing with the identification and selection of indicators (**section 2.2**). Figure 2 provides an overview of the various steps followed and their interrelationship.

Figure 2. Outline of the different steps of the methodology and the relationship between them.

2.1 Classification definition

During the literature screening, a classification was developed according to different areas of concern and using a hierarchical structure in order to map the wide range of sustainability issues. The classification consists of four levels: pillars, key areas, subareas, and indicators (or requirements). The key areas and subareas have been defined on the basis of the sustainability aspects reported in various sources, including standards (EFRAG, 2022; UNE, 2016; UNI, 2022), research calls (Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU), 2023; European Commission, 2022a), policies (European Commission, 2020; EEA, 2016), relevant reports (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2023a; FAO, 2019; OECD, 2020a; UNEP Life Cycle Initiative and Social LC Alliance, 2020), outputs from other related projects (Golaszewski et al., 2020; Hasenheit et al., 2016; Ladu and Morone, 2021; Leire Iriarte and Fritsche, 2015a; Matthias Stratmann et al., 2022), scientific publications (Neugebauer et al., 2016), monitoring systems, and certification schemes. Figure 3 below, show the structure of the classification. A detailed explanation of the classification and its rationale can be found in section 3.

Figure 3. Layout of the classification structure according to the four-level hierarchy, where “I” stands for indicator (fourth level).

This initial classification was validated through a workshop organized by the STAR4BBS project on May 26, 2023. This collaborative workshop brought together 27 participants from diverse backgrounds, including EU policy makers, intergovernmental organizations, academia, value chain actors, civil society groups, certification organizations, and end-users. As part of the workshop, USC led an open discussion on the classification aimed to validate and enhance it. The valuable insights gathered during the workshop contribute to refine the classification. Further details of this workshop session and its results are reported in Appendix A1 (e.g., a copy of the feedback received via the Miro board and the slides shown to participants during the session). Additionally, a second activity, this time among the STAR4BBS partners, was carried out to align the classification of indicators with the policy targets selected by nova-Institute in WP1 (section 3.5). Appendix A2 includes all materials related to the activity.

2.2 Identification and selection of LCA-based indicators

An analysis of the relevant literature was conducted to identify LCA indicators related to the three pillars of sustainability. Given the different levels of maturity of each dimension of LCA, a tailored analysis approach was adopted for each pillar.

Environmental LCA approach

Environmental LCA (E-LCA), commonly referred to simply as Life Cycle Assessment, focuses on the environmental impacts along the supply chain, from the extraction of raw materials to the end-of-life of products and services. Notably, environmental LCA is the most developed branch of life cycle methodologies (Sala et al., 2021) and it is standardized by the international ISO 14040 and 14044 standards, providing a general framework for LCA practitioners. In addition, much effort has been made in the LCA community to harmonize methodology to provide a common basis for all LCA practitioners and technical experts to produce consistent, reliable and comparable

results. As a result, different guidelines have been implemented, providing specific recommendations on data collection, systems modeling, indicators to be used for impact assessment, quality assessments and communication of results. The documents referred to are the International Life Cycle Data System (ILCD) Handbook (J. R. C. European Commission, 2012), the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) framework (Manfredi et al., 2012) and the UNEP-SETAC Life Cycle Initiative Guidelines (UNEP-SETAC Life Cycle Initiative, 2019a, 2019b). Because of their relevance, authority in the field of LCA and the fact that they already provide an important knowledge filter, they were selected as target documents for deriving environmental LCA indicators.

- **ILCD Handbook**

The ILCD Handbook has been developed by the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission in accordance with ISO standards as a more detailed technical guide for conducting LCA studies (European Commission, 2023c). The Handbook consists of several volumes, each focusing on a specific methodological topic related to the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) and Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) phases.

- **PEF framework**

The PEF framework, based on the ISO 14040 series and the ILCD handbook (Manfredi et al., 2012), aims to provide specific guidance to companies on how to assess and communicate the environmental performance of their products and, indirectly, to ensure reliable environmental reporting to public authorities and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) (Directorate-General for Environment, 2021; European Commission, 2013).

- **UNEP-SETAC Life Cycle Initiative guideline**

The Life Cycle Initiative, founded by the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and the Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry (SETAC), is a "public-private, multi-stakeholder partnership" (Life Cycle Initiative, 2023) working to establish a science-based (through the involvement of over 100 scientists) international consensus on indicators for assessing environmental impacts throughout the life cycle (Jolliet et al., 2018). The resulting guidelines from its ongoing work provide practical recommendations on agreed environmental indicators and LCIA characterization factors (UNEP-SETAC Life Cycle Initiative, 2019a, 2019b).

Economic LCA approach

To successfully establish sustainable bio-based value chains, it is essential to include the assessment of the economic performance, which is undoubtedly a primary objective in business. Two main methodologies, Life Cycle Costing and Techno-Economic Analysis are widely used to perform such assessment.

The methodology of Life Cycle Costing (LCC) analyzes the sum of all costs of a product, activity or service over its entire life cycle, including acquisition, operation, and end-of-life costs (European Commission, 2023d). In addition, it may also include the cost of externalities, such as environmental and social impacts. On the other hand, the

Techno-Economic Analysis (TEA) approach assesses both the technical and economic performance of products, processes and services (Mahmud et al., 2021a). Although TEA does not have an inherent life cycle perspective (typically limited to the boundaries of a cradle-to-gate system), it can be adapted to follow the life cycle perspective of LCA (Mahmud et al., 2021b). Both methodologies share many indicators (Mahmud et al., 2021b), although due to the strong cost focus of LCC, many indicators related to the technical feasibility are left behind by LCC.

In this context, one of the objectives of this deliverable is to provide a robust set of economic indicators (hereafter referred to as indicators that address both economic and technical aspects) that are tailored to the bio-based systems. To this end, indicators were retrieved from well-established chemical engineering books. In particular, “Analysis, Synthesis and Design of Chemical Processes” (Turton et al., 2018) and “Plant design and economics for chemical engineers” (Peters et al., 2003) were analyzed due to their well-developed methods and widespread use in the field of process design and TEA. In addition, the indicators identified in these two books were supplemented with indicators from research papers, databases (OECD, 2023) and other relevant EU projects to ensure a comprehensive coverage of the pillar and to include different measurement approaches (see the Appendix section B1).

Social LCA approach

In 2009, the first Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) of Products were published, setting the initial pathway for the standardization of the evaluation of social and socio-economic impacts under a life cycle perspective. The guidelines views social impacts as consequences of social interactions in the context of one activity (production, consumption, or disposal) and/or caused by it and/or by the prevention or reinforcement of actions conducted by stakeholders (e.g., the implementation of safety measures in a facility) (Rebolledo-Leiva et al., 2023). The abovementioned document defines the S-LCA methodology as an impact assessment tool that evaluates the social and socio-economic aspects (positive and/or negative) of products throughout their life cycle. In this way, the methodological framework follows, with certain particularities, the same four-step procedure of the ISO framework 14040-14044 of the environmental LCA approach. In 2020, the UNEP and the life cycle initiative published an updated version entitled “Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of products and organizations” to define a new frame of reference due to the absence of consensus on S-LCA and proposing the initial pathway on the organizational perspective.

In this deliverable the following methodological approach was implemented in order to identify the social LCA indicators:

- Studies identification and database search: a search was conducted in well-known scientific databases like Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus using the sets of keywords “bioeconomy”, “bioproduct”, “S-LCA”, “social life cycle assessment”, “bio-based”, “biofuels”, “social LCA”, “bioenergy”, among others. The period selected for evaluation corresponds to those articles published before 2022 (i.e., until 2021 included).

- Article management: all manuscripts were handled through the Mendeley® software, and all articles duplicated were removed.
- Screening title, abstract, and keywords: all the titles, abstracts, and keywords of each article were analyzed to determine their suitability for the topic. Articles published in a language other than English were removed, as well as those not related to the scope of STAR4BBS project (e.g., bioenergy, biofuels, biorefineries) and with no access (e.g., Conference papers).
- Full-text reading (eligibility): after selection, the full texts were read. The decision to retain or exclude articles was based on whether they used the life cycle approach in the social assessment of bioeconomy, following both available guidelines.

A total of 55 articles were considered as the final sample. From them, 43 articles were analyzed (see the Appendix section B2) to collect the social indicators as the remaining studies were review articles and book chapters.

Socioeconomic and social implications can be grouped based on five stakeholders' dimensions: workers, consumers, local community, society, and value-chain actors. Based on the stakeholders, both inventory data and impact method must be specified. From each article of the sample, the stakeholders, subcategories/social themes, and indicators analyzed or proposed (if corresponding) were collected. Furthermore, the bio-based value chains as well as the scope under study were also identified.

Data collection

Three separate databases (consisting of Excel® spreadsheets) were created to collect all the information obtained throughout the analysis. The parameters collected include a brief description of each indicator, the metric or characterization model used, the unit of measurement and the source from which the indicator was obtained. In addition, each indicator was classified according to the predefined key areas and subareas of sustainability (see section 3) and the sector and life cycle stage to which it applies. Sectors were categorized according to the Bioeconomy Strategy (European Commission, 2018) as *Agriculture, Forestry, Fishing and Aquaculture, Bio-based Textiles, Wood products and Furniture, Paper, Bio-based chemicals* and *Pharmaceuticals, plastics and rubber*, while life cycle stages were defined as *Feedstock, Materials & products*, and *End-of-Life*. Additionally, the impact category (to which the indicator belongs) was specified for environmental indicators and the measurement type (qualitative/quantitative) for social indicators. A description of each parameter is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Description of the parameters gathered in the databases and two examples from the environmental and social pillar, respectively.

Parameter	Definition of parameter	Example 1	Example 2
Indicator	The quantitative, qualitative, or binary variable that can be measured or described (BS EN 16751:2016)	Radiative forcing as global warming potential (GWP100)	Percentage of workers who have been provided training in health and safety by the employers

Table 1 (cont.). Description of the parameters gathered in the databases and two examples from the environmental and social pillar, respectively.

Parameter	Definition of parameter	Example 1	Example 2
Indicator description	A brief explanation of what the indicators represent.	Increase in the average global temperature resulting from greenhouse gas emissions (GHG)	-
Type of indicator	To specified whether the indicator is measure with qualitative or quantitative metrics.	Quantitative	Quantitative
Metric/characterization on model	The metric, equation or model used to measure the indicators.	Baseline model of 100 years of the IPCC (based on IPCC 2013)	-
Unit	The unit of measurement of the indicator.	kg CO ₂ eq	%
Key area	The corresponding key area of the defined classification (section 3).	Climate change	Workers
Subarea	The corresponding subarea of the defined classification (section 3).	GHG emissions	Occupational health and safety
Impact category	The classes used on E-LCA to represent environmental issues of concern (ISO, 2006). This parameter is only reported for environmental indicators.	Climate change	-
Sector	Bioeconomy sectors where the indicator can be applied. The bioeconomy sectors are those identified in the Bioeconomy Strategy and include <i>Agriculture, Forestry, Fishing and Aquaculture, Bio-based Textiles, Wood products and Furniture, Paper, Bio-based chemicals and Pharmaceuticals, plastics and rubber</i>	All	All
Life cycle stage	The different periods in the lifetime of a system. Three life cycle stages are distinguished: 1) Feedstock, which refers to the stage at which resources are acquired; 2) Materials & Products, including the production, distribution and use of materials/products; 3) End of life, which involves the disposal or valorization of the product/material at the end of its useful life.	All	All

Final selection of indicators

Upon completion of the literature analysis and data collection, a comprehensive set of LCA indicators was carefully selected for each pillar: environmental, social, and economic. The selection process followed predefined criteria to ensure that the selected indicators were appropriate and accurately reflected the desired aspects of sustainability. Based on the methodology for selecting indicators reported by the Joint Research Centre (Vidal-Legaz et al., 2016) and the INDECO project (Reyntjens and Brown, 2005), a total of four criteria were applied, which are described in detail below:

Criterion 1. **Relevance.** The selected indicators must be in line with the scope of the project and cover relevant aspects of sustainability for bio-based systems. In this sense, the indicators must be consistent with the key areas and subareas of sustainability highlighted in section 3.

Criterion 2. **Operability.** The indicators must be easily measurable, with readily available data, models, and calculation methods. For environmental LCA indicators, it is important to consider the availability of methods in SimaPro (the most widely used LCA software for environmental assessment) to ensure the feasibility and practicality of measuring the indicators.

Criterion 3. **Robustness & reliability.** The indicators should be up-to-date and validated by experts in the field. Priority will be given to indicators recommended by authoritative institutions recognized for their expertise in sustainability assessment. This criterion ensures that the selected indicators are based on the latest scientific knowledge and have a high level of credibility. Examples of recommended indicators could be those proposed by organizations such as the Joint Research Centre or the UNEP-SETAC Life Cycle Initiative.

Criterion 4. **Avoiding Overlaps.** The final set of indicators should not include indicators that measure the same specific aspect of sustainability. By avoiding duplication, the assessment becomes more streamlined and focused on capturing different aspects of sustainability. For instance, if energy consumption is already covered by one indicator, there may be no need to include another indicator that specifically measures electricity requirements. In the case of the social pillar, an exception was deliberately made and several indicators measuring the same specific aspect were included. This was done to ensure that, in the event of missing data, there would be alternatives for evaluating those aspects.

By adhering to these criteria, the selected indicators for assessing the sustainability of bio-based systems will effectively cover the relevant aspects of sustainability, be easily measurable, validated by experts and free of redundancies.

3 Classification: key sustainability areas

As mentioned above, a hierarchical four-level classification was defined to organize the indicators according to the sustainability areas of concern. In total, four pillars were considered: *Environmental*, *Circularity*, *Social* and *Economic*, each of which was further subdivided into several key areas and subareas to give more specificity Figure 4. A detailed explanation of the components of the classification and the rationale for each pillar is presented in the following section.

Figure 4. Layout of the pillars and key areas of the classification.

3.1 Environmental pillar

The environmental pillar is structured into seven key areas covering different environmental issues: *Climate Change*, *Air*, *Water*, *Soil*, *Biodiversity*, *Natural Resources* and *Hazardous Substances* (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. Layout of the key areas and subareas of the environmental pillar.

Climate change

Includes indicators focused on prevention, mitigation and adaptation strategies to climate change. They are divided into:

- **High carbon stock areas.** It includes indicators that measure the use of high-carbon stock areas (either above or below ground), such as wetlands and forests, to conduct business.
- **GHG emissions.** The indicators comprised here focus on the quantification and reduction of greenhouse gas emissions (GHG), and the assessment of GHG-related impacts. Indicators measuring substitution effects, i.e., the avoided fossil GHG emissions by using bio-based products instead of other fossil-intensive products or fossil energy, are also included here, as well as indirect land use change (iLUC) emissions.
- **GHG mitigation.** It encompasses indicators that assess strategies that remove greenhouse gases from the Earth's atmosphere through natural or technological solutions, including carbon sequestration in soils.
- **Adaptation strategies.** It includes indicators that measure strategies to prevent or minimize the adverse effects of climate change.

Air

Includes indicators that measure issues related to the atmosphere. It consists of a single subarea:

- **Air quality**, focused on the air pollution status.

Water

Contains indicators that measure issues related to the hydrosphere.

- **Water quality** focuses on the chemical, physical, and biological condition of water, both fresh and marine.
- **Water depletion** addresses the amount of water used and the potential long-term water-level decline in water levels.

Soil

Includes indicators that address soil concerns.

- **Soil quality** focuses on the physical, chemical and biological conditions of the soil.
- **Soil depletion** is concerned with soil erosion and soil loss.

Biodiversity

The indicators included in this key area measure issues related to biodiversity, i.e., the variability among living organisms at all its levels (from genes to ecosystems), with the aim of knowing the state of biodiversity and restoring, conserving and enhancing it.

- **Species diversity.** This includes indicators that measure biodiversity at the species level, including strategies focusing on restoring, preserving and protecting specific species.

- **Ecosystems diversity.** It incorporates indicators that measure biodiversity at the ecosystem level, including strategies to restore, preserve and strengthen ecosystems, such as not operating in no-go areas.

Natural resources

This key area includes a set of indicators that address the sustainable use and depletion of natural resources, as well as the use of certified raw materials. In this approach, natural resources are understood as material and non-material assets occurring in nature that are at some point in time deemed useful for humans (Beylot et al., 2020; Sonderegger et al., 2017).

- **Abiotic resources** stands for non-living resources, in particular minerals, metals, fossil fuels and energy. The indicators included here only consider their use (with a focus on potential depletion), while the circularity dimension (in the following subsection 3.2) evaluates the efficiency of their use (*resource-efficiency*) and their renewability (*renewable resources*).
- **Biotic resources** are living organisms: crops, fish, wood, etc. Here, indicators measure the sustainability of the harvest to ensure future supply.
- **Land use.** Land use covers both land occupation and transformation pressures.
- **Ecosystem services** are the benefits that people derive from ecosystems (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2003). These indicators assess the loss and/or degradation of ecosystem services.

Hazardous substances

It includes indicators covering toxicity effects (e.g., human toxicity), and presence of hazards/toxins in waste, products, and materials. In the case of indicators measuring presence or emissions of hazards in air, water, or soil, they are classified in respective *air*, *water* and *soil* key areas.

- **Human toxicity** includes indicators that quantify toxic effects on human health.
- **Presence of hazardous substances** covers the existence of hazards/toxins in the materials/resources used, products and wastes.

3.2 Circularity pillar

Based on the life cycle stage at which a circularity strategy applies, the circularity dimension is organized into four key areas (Figure 6):

Products and materials design

Indicators included here measure strategies for designing products and materials to comply with circularity principles of prolonging their lifespan and maintaining their value.

- **Durability** refers to prolonging the life of the product/material at the stage of use without losing their functionality or appeal (e.g., by resisting wear, being reusable, making it upgradeable or repairable, or retaining its emotional value). It also

includes modularity strategies, which refers to the design approach that allows products to be broken down into modular components that can be easily assembled, disassembled, replaced, or upgraded, ultimately extending the life of the product.

- **Efficiency** focuses on designing products that use resources more efficiently. It also refers to strategies aimed at reducing the resources needed to produce a given product/material. The latter is often referred to as dematerialization and includes design strategies such as light weighting, downsizing or the use of alternative materials.
- **Closed-loop design** covers strategies dealing with the end-of-life stage of products and materials to keep them in the economic system as long as possible. For instance, redistribution, refurbishment, remanufacturing, and recycling (e.g., composting).

Figure 6. Layout of the key areas and subareas of the circularity pillar.

Production processes

It contains indicators addressing circular strategies at the manufacturing stage.

- **Renewable resources** focuses on the degree of renewability of the resources.
- **Resource-efficiency** focuses on maintaining resources in use throughout the production chain through strategies such as cascading flows and the use of secondary/recycled resources.
- **Resource cycling** focuses on maintaining resources in use through the production chain, measuring strategies such as cascading and the use of secondary/recycled resources.

End-of-life stage

The circular strategies applied to waste management during business operations are the focus of the indicators included here.

- **Waste prevention** brings together indicators that focus on actions taken to prevent the generation of waste.

- **Waste management** includes indicators that address how waste is managed through recovery operations (e.g., reuse, recycling, or composting) and disposal operations (e.g., landfilling, incineration).

Circular business model

This key area goes beyond specific life cycle stages to focus on the entire business from a circular design perspective.

- **Industrial symbiosis** includes indicators that address synergies between two or more entities to improve their circularity.
- **Business model** contains indicators that focus on circular business models, such as shifting to a pay-for-use (service) model rather than pay-for-ownership (consumption) and virtualization of the product.

3.3 Economic pillar

The economic pillar consists of four key areas that represent essential aspects of economic sustainability (see *Figure 7*).

Figure 7. Layout of the key areas and subareas of the economic pillar.

Profitability

Includes indicators that address the value created by the business.

- **Revenue** covers the monetary value generated from business performance and success, including costs, benefits, and revenues. Capital costs are not covered by *profitability* as they are accounted within the key area *long-term investment*.
- **Feedstock functionality** addresses the added value (i.e., the enhancement of a good or service by improving its quality/function and making it worth more than the raw material used) achieved as a function of the resources required for the production process.

Long-term Investment

Indicators focus on the long-term economic plan of the company.

- **Capital investment** includes the technical development and the financial investment.
- **External fundings** refers to the external financing of the company by means of funds.
- **Investment efficiency** deals with the optimal plant capacity for the evaluation of economies of scale.
- **Innovation & Development** deals with the company's involvement in innovation and development activities in order to offer new or improved products and services or to enhance its operations at various stages.

Productivity

Encompasses indicators measuring the relation between the resources and personnel-effort inputs and the volume of outputs.

- **Material & energy-related productivity** focuses on resource productivity.
- **Human-related productivity** focuses on the productivity of the workforce.

Economic risks

Includes indicators measuring the risks and uncertainties, which are inherent in new investments and initiatives. The risk assessment prompts more informed and reasonable choices since it indicates any possible unwanted outcomes leading to potential economic loss (Gargalo et al., 2016).

- **Economic & technical risks** take into account the viability of the process and the uncertainties that may arise during the operation of the plant.

3.4 Social pillar

In the social pillar, the key areas are organized according to the different stakeholder groups (e.g., workers), from which various subareas are derived that reflect their specific concerns (Figure 8).

Workers

- **Child labor** addresses both children and young workers, and it refers to work that, in terms of UNEP Life Cycle Initiative & Social LC Alliance (2020), is:
 1. Mentally, physically, socially or morally hazardous and harmful to children and young workers.
 2. Deprives them of the opportunity to attend school.
 3. Forcing them to leave school prematurely.
 4. Forcing them to try to combine school attendance with excessively long and hard work.
- **Freedom of association and collective bargaining** includes the right of workers to strike, the rights of organizations to draw up their constitutions and rules, to elect their representatives in full freedom, to organize their activity freely, and to formulate their programs. Discriminations due to trade union association and communication of grievances are included here.
- **Forced labor** is any work or service that is performed involuntarily and under threat of any kind of punishment (ILO, 1913).
- **Working conditions** refers to work-related conditions including working hours, worker-management dialogue, temporary work practices, flexible conditions (to reconcile with personal life), trainings (except for those made for health and safety purposes) and complaint mechanisms.
- **Fair salary** includes the amount of the wage and other related aspects (regularity of payments, etc.).
- **Mental or physical abuse** refers to verbal and non-verbal behaviors. Sexual harassment is included.
- **Equal opportunities/ Discrimination** addresses whether all workers are treated fairly and have equal opportunities, regardless their age, sex, race, disabilities, marital status, pregnancy, family status, family responsibilities, religious, political beliefs, sexual orientation.
- **Occupational health and safety** include the prevention of health problems and risks caused by working conditions (e.g., through training), the provision of a healthy and safe working environment, and healthy and safe living conditions.
- **Social benefits/social security** includes retirement, disability, dependents, and survivors' benefits, medical insurance, paid maternity and paternity leaves, and paid sick leaves.
- **Employment relationship** refers to “the legal link between employers and employees” (UNEP Life Cycle Initiative and Social LC Alliance, 2020). All aspects related to contracts are considered here, including the type of contract.

Consumers

- **Health and safety of end users** covers the extent to what selling services or products are safe and healthy for consumers.
- **Feedback mechanisms.** It refers to the tools provided to consumers to communicate with the company. Tool examples are surveys, return policies, quality assurances, guarantees, warranties.

- **Transparency** addresses the way companies inform consumers about their products without misleading them.
- **Product benefits** refers to features in the products/services that benefit consumers, such as limiting the use of additives in food products.

Local community

- **Migration** assesses whether organizations contribute to delocalization, migration, or “involuntary resettlement” within communities and whether populations are treated adequately.
- **Health and safety** includes general safety conditions and their public health impacts (e.g., structural failures). The effect of hazardous substances and pollution emissions on human health are assigned to the environmental pillar.
- **Community engagement** covers dialogue mechanisms, including community concerns within business plans, involvement in community activities, financial support of community projects, engagement in welfare programs. Training is included in *contribution to employment* subarea.
- **Land use rights** address the extent to which organizations respect and work to protect land use rights. In the cases an indicator addresses the land use rights of indigenous people, it is classified in *respect of indigenous rights* subarea.
- **Respect of indigenous rights** includes the right of the indigenous groups (people) to lands, resources, cultural integrity, self-determination, and self-government.
- **Cultural heritage** covers elements such as language, social and religious practices, knowledge and traditional craftsmanship, as well as cultural spaces and objects.
- **Access to resources** assesses the extent to which organizations respect, work to protect, to provide or to improve community access to local material and immaterial resources. Material resources stand for water, mineral, biological resources, and infrastructure (i.e., roads, sanitation facilities, schools, etc.). Immaterial resources refer to community services, intellectual property rights, freedom of expression, and access to information.
- **Contribution to employment** covers whether companies promote local employment by hiring local employees and providing training to locals.
- **Contribution to economic development** by generating revenue and making investments.
- **Secure living conditions** against human rights violations by being complicit or displaying inaction.

Society

- **Contribution to economic development.** Unlike in *local community* key area, this subarea refers to a broader economic impact on society.
- **Technology development** assesses if the organization contributes to technology development, by engaging in partnerships with other organizations (e.g., universities, laboratories, institutions, centers) in joint research and development programs or private-public partnerships to develop supporting infrastructure and promote the facilitation of sustainable business models.

- **Poverty alleviation** evaluates the presence or not of pro-active activities, such as strategies, action plans, investment, to reduce the poverty of the society at different geographical levels made by the organization.
- **Food security** addresses the risk of promoting food insecurity by using biomass for other purposes than feed and food.

Value chain actors

- **Fair competition in the market** includes price fixing, bid rigging, creation of market or output restrictions, imposition of geographic quotas, or allocation of customers, suppliers, geographic areas, and product lines with the purpose of limiting the effects of market competition.
- **Promoting social responsibility** encompasses how companies engage with their suppliers, ensuring adherence to ethical values, human rights, and the well-being of society. It involves encouraging suppliers to align their actions with these principles and fostering a responsible business environment.
- **Supplier relationships** relates to agreements that regulate the exchanges, trade, and relation among organizations.
- **Respect of intellectual property rights** refers to industrial and scientific property rights, such as patents, copyrights, trademarks.
- **Wealth distribution** evaluates the extent to which the value is distributed in an equitable way among all the actors of the value chain.

- **Fraud in the supply chain** refers to deceptive or dishonest practices. It involves intentional misrepresentation, manipulation, concealment of information or activities with the aim of gaining unfair advantages, financial benefits, or evading legal and ethical obligations.

Figure 8. Layout of the key areas and subareas of the social pillar.

Considering the major sources used to define the proposed subareas (Table 2), a mapping of the reported subareas from each source is provided in Table 3.

Table 2. Sources used for the mapping of the proposed subareas.

Code	Source	Reference
1	UNE-EN 16751. Bio-based products. Sustainability criteria	(UNE, 2016)
2	Integrated Assessment Tool (IAT)	(Golaszewski et al., 2020)
3	BioSTEP project	(Hasenheit et al., 2016)
4	S2biom project	(Leire Iriarte and Fritsche, 2015b)

Table 2 (cont.). Sources used for the mapping of the proposed subareas.

Code	Source	Reference
5	Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU) Annual Work Programme 2023	(CBE JU, 2023)
6	Study of the environmental sustainability requirements of bio-based value chains and supply chains for bio-based industry in future EU funded R&I demonstration and flagship projects	(Matthias Stratmann et al., 2022)
7	Clean environment and zero pollution (HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION-01)	(European Commission, 2022b)
8	Indicators to monitor and evaluate the sustainability of bioeconomy - overview of a proposed way forward	(FAO, 2019)
9	UNI/PdR 135:2022. Bio-based products-Organization and product application guidelines for environmental and social qualification	(UNI, 2022)
10	A new Circular Economy Action Plan For a cleaner and more competitive Europe	(European Commission, 2020)
11	Circular economy principles	(Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2023b)
12	Circular economy in Europe - developing the knowledge base	(EEA, 2016)
13	The OECD Inventory of Circular Economy indicators	(OECD, 2020b)
14	Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Organizations 2020	(UNEP Life Cycle Initiative and Social LC Alliance, 2020)
15	European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS) E5 Resource use and circular economy	(EFRAG, 2022)
16	From Life Cycle Costing to Economic Life Cycle Assessment—Introducing an Economic Impact Pathway	(Neugebauer et al., 2016)

Table 3. Overview of the subareas reported in 16 different sources. A color was assigned according to the dimension of sustainability under which the source addresses the subarea. Color legend: environmental (green), circularity (yellow), economic (blue), social (pink), others (grey).

Pillar	Key area	Subarea	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	
ENVIRONMENTAL	Climate change	High carbon stock areas				Green	Green	Green		Green							Green		
		GHG emissions	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Grey	Green	Green	Yellow				Yellow		Green	
		GHG mitigation	Green				Green			Grey									
		Adaptation strategies									Green								Green
	Air	Air quality	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Grey	Green	Green							Green	
	Water	Water quality	Green	Grey	Green	Green							Green						
		Water depletion	Green	Grey	Green	Green					Yellow		Green						
	Soil	Soil quality	Green	Grey	Green			Yellow					Green						
		Soil depletion	Green	Grey	Green								Green						
	Biodiversity	Species diversity	Green	Grey	Green	Green		Yellow					Green						
		Ecosystems diversity	Green	Grey	Green	Green		Yellow					Green						
	Natural resources	Abiotic resources		Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Grey	Green	Green		Yellow		Yellow			
		Biotic resources									Green			Yellow					Green
		Land use		Grey	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Grey	Green								Green
		Ecosystem services			Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Grey	Green								Green
	Hazardous substances	Human toxicity		Green						Grey	Pink								Green
Presence of hazardous substances			Grey	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Grey	Green		Yellow	Yellow	Yellow				Green	
CIRCULAR	Product & materials design	Durability									Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow			Green	
		Efficiency										Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow				
		Closed-loop design		Grey	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Grey	Green	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow			Green
	Production processes	Renewable resources	Green	Grey	Green	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow			Green						
		Resource-efficiency	Green	Grey	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Grey	Green	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow			Green
		Resource cycling		Grey	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Grey	Green	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow			Green
	End-of-life stage	Waste prevention		Grey	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Grey	Green	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow			Green
		Waste management	Green	Grey	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Grey	Green	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow			Green

Table 3 (cont.). Overview of the subareas reported in 16 different sources. A color was assigned according to the dimension of sustainability under which the source addresses the subarea. Color legend: environmental (green), circularity (yellow), economic (blue), social (pink), others (grey).

Pillar	Key area	Subarea	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	
ECONOMIC	Circular business model	Industrial symbiosis																	
		Business model																	
ECONOMIC	Profitability	Revenue																	
		Feedstock functionality																	
	Long-term investment	Capital investment																	
		External fundings																	
		Investment efficiency																	
	Productivity	Innovation & Development																	
		Material & energy-related productivity																	
	Economic risks	Human-related productivity																	
		Economic & technical risks																	
SOCIAL	Workers	Freedom of association and collective bargaining																	
		Child labour																	
		Forced labour																	
		Working conditions																	
		Fair salary																	
		Mental or physical abuse																	
		Equal opportunities/Discrimination																	
		Occupational health and safety																	
		Social benefits/social security																	
		Employment relationship																	
	Consumers	Health and safety of end users																	
		Transparency																	
		Feedback mechanisms																	
		Product benefits																	

Table 3 (cont.). Overview of the subareas reported in 16 different sources. A color was assigned according to the dimension of sustainability under which the source addresses the subarea. Color legend: environmental (green), circularity (yellow), economic (blue), social (pink), others (grey).

Pillar	Key area	Subarea	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16			
SOCIAL	Local community	Land use rights																			
		Respect of indigenous rights																			
		Access to resources																			
		Secure living conditions																			
		Migration																			
		Cultural heritage																			
		Health and safety of local community																			
		Community engagement																			
		Contribution to employment																			
		Contribution to economic development																			
		Food security																			
	Society	Contribution to economic development																			
		Poverty alleviation																			
		Technology development																			
	Value chain actors	Fair competition in the market																			
		Promoting social responsibility																			
		Supplier relationships																			
		Respect of intellectual property rights																			
		Wealth distribution																			
	Fraud in the supply chain																				

An internal activity within the STAR4BBS consortium was carried out to align the selected policy targets (D 1.1) with the defined sustainability areas (key areas and subareas) (see Appendix A2 to access to all materials related to the activity). The following is a compilation of the identified 14 sustainability policy targets:

1. By 2030, at least 20% of the carbon used in chemicals and plastic products should come from sustainable non-fossil sources.
2. Reach a 55% reduction in GHG emissions by 2030.
3. At least 45% of the energy in the EU comes from renewable sources by 2030.
4. Reach climate neutrality by 2050.
5. Reduce the overall use and risk of chemical pesticides by 50% by 2030.
6. Reduce the use of fertilizers by at least 20% by 2030.
7. By 2050, 5% of the energy used in aviation should come from advanced biofuels.
8. Increase the sustainability of products in the EU starting from its design/inception and ensure the sustainability of renewable bio-based materials.
9. Establish a product performance on energy use and efficiency, recyclability and environmental impact.
10. Ensure the sustainability of renewable bio-based materials.
11. Make sustainable management of soils the norm across the EU.
12. Set out conditions to ensure that the environmental impact of the production and consumption of bio-based, biodegradable and compostable plastics is positive.
13. Provide definitions and criteria to determine which economic activities are environmentally sustainable.
14. Introduce sustainability criteria for biomass and biogas.

The resulting matching matrix, shown in Table 4, reflects the positive and negative relationship between the policy targets and the sustainability areas. A *positive relation* was considered to exist when the sustainability area, in particular the subareas, contribute to the achievement of the policy target or where the area is improved by the achievement of the policy target. On the other hand, a negative relationship is reported when there are potential trade-offs between the policy targets and the sustainability area (e.g., a sustainability area penalizes the achievement of a policy target). For example, the key area *climate change* can contribute to the achievement of the policy target 1 “By 2030, at least 20% of the carbon used in chemicals and plastic products should come from sustainable non-fossil sources”, while the policy target 3 “At least 45% of the energy in the EU comes from renewable sources by 2030” may pose a risk to the depletion of biotic resources. Scenarios where both relationships occur were also reflected in the matrix. The matching matrix could potentially be used to prioritize certain key areas/subareas within the monitoring system or to communicate the results of the monitoring system in the light of the policies.

Table 4. Matching matrix between the policy targets and the sustainability areas. Green color: positive relationship (e.g., the category/subcategory obtained at least one black star and no red stars); red color: negative relationship (e.g., the category/subcategory obtained at least one red star and no black stars); yellow color: positive and negative relationship (e.g., the category/subcategory obtained at least one red star and one black star).

Pillar	Key area	Subarea	01	02	03	04	05	06	07	08	09	10	11	12	13	14	
ENVIRONMENTAL	Climate change	High carbon stock areas	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	
		GHG emissions	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
		GHG mitigation	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
		Adaptation strategies	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	Air	Air quality	●	●	●		●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
		Water	Water quality			●		●				●	●	●	●	●	●
	Water depletion		●		●						●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	Soil	Soil quality	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
		Soil depletion	●	●	●		●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	Biodiversity	Species diversity	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
		Ecosystems diversity	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	Natural resources	Abiotic resources	●	●	●				●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
		Biotic resources		●	●					●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
		Land use	●							●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
		Ecosystem services		●	●			●		●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	Hazardous substances	Human toxicity	●					●			●	●			●	●	●
Presence of hazardous substances		●					●			●	●			●	●	●	
CIRCULAR	Production processes		●	●						●	●	●		●	●	●	
	End-of-life stage		●		●					●	●	●	●	●	●	●	
	Product & materials design		●							●	●	●	●	●	●	●	
	Circular business model									●	●	●		●	●	●	
ECONOMIC	Profitability	●					●	●		●		●		●	●	●	
	Long-term investment										●	●		●	●	●	
	Productivity				●	●	●					●		●	●	●	
	Economic risks																
SOCIAL	Workers			●						●		●		●	●	●	
	Consumers			●						●	●	●		●	●	●	
	Local community	●	●	●						●		●		●	●	●	
	Society	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	
	Value chain actors									●	●	●		●	●	●	

4 LCA indicators

4.1 Environmental LCA indicators

By limiting the search to specific, highly relevant sources in the field, a manageable number of environmental indicators were collected. A total of 56 indicators were retrieved (Appendix C1), reduced to 39 indicators after eliminating those that were repeated or did not specify the method or model followed. Indicators were found for all key areas, but some subareas were not represented by an indicator, namely *high carbon stock areas*, *GHG removal* and *adaptation under climate change*; *ecosystem diversity* under *biodiversity*; *biotic resource*, *land use* and *ecosystem services* under *natural resources*; and *presence of hazardous substances* under *hazardous substances*. The lack of LCA indicators for these subareas was expected, as these issues have not (yet) been addressed in the environmental LCA methodology or are at an early stage of development (e.g., ecosystem services) (Ndue and Pál, 2022; Rugani et al., 2023). Figure 9 shows the subareas for which LCA indicators were identified.

Figure 9. Distribution of environmental LCA indicators by subarea.

Water quality, abiotic resources, human toxicity, and to a lesser extent, soil quality and air quality had the highest diversity of indicators, while indicators related to GHG emissions and water depletion had a narrower range. This discrepancy is mainly due to the broader range of specific impacts and stressors that are addressed by the indicators in the subareas with a higher number of indicators. For instance, the water quality subarea includes indicators measuring eutrophication and ecotoxicity effects on both marine and freshwater biota, and the abiotic resources subarea includes various indicators addressing specific abiotic resources that may be affected by human activities.

Another potential reason is that some subareas include indicators that assess the same impacts but use different characterization models. As an example, the water depletion subarea includes two indicators measuring potential water deprivation, one (Weighted user deprivation potential) uses Available Water REmaining (AWARE) model, while the other (Water use related to local scarcity of water) follows the Swiss Ecological Scarcity Method. Most of the identified indicators apply to all life cycle stages and sectors of the bioeconomy, although there are a few that are limited to specific stages. For example, the indicator Soil Quality Index addresses impacts at the feedstock production and end-of-life stages (De Laurentiis et al., 2019).

Selected environmental LCA indicators

Table 5 shows the final selection of environmental LCA indicators according with the predefined criteria: relevance, operability, robustness and reliability, and overlap avoidance (section 2.2). All the selected indicators align with the PEF framework and to a lesser extent with ILCD Handbook and UNEP-SETAC Life Cycle Initiative guidelines. This is because the indicators recommended by the PEF framework are at a more advanced stage of development and are therefore more robust. As the PEF framework has been created by the European Commission with the objective of providing consistent and comparable LCA results, aligning the selected indicators with PEF enhances the likelihood that the results from the STAR4BBS project will be valuable for conducting future case study comparisons. In addition, this alignment ensures that the results can be effectively used for benchmarking the sustainability performance across different sectors in the bioeconomy. Furthermore, special consideration was given to the inclusion of the indicator measuring biodiversity loss ("Potential species loss"). As recommended by the UNEP-SETAC Life Cycle Initiative guidelines, the potential loss of species could be measured using the characterization factors of Land Use and Land Use Change impact categories, as these factors inherently include the biodiversity assessment.

Table 5. Selection of environmental LCA indicators. (1) PEF Framework, (2) ILCD Handbook, (3) Life Cycle Initiative, (Other) From reference indicated in the Metrics/ Characterization model/Reference box.

Key area	Subarea	Indicator	Impact category	Description	Metrics/ Characterization model/Reference	Unit	Stage	Sector	1	2	3
Climate change	GHG emissions	Radiative forcing as global warming potential (GWP100)	Climate change	Increase in the average global temperature resulting from greenhouse gas emissions	Baseline model of 100 years of the IPCC (based on IPCC 2013)	kg CO ₂ eq	All	All			
Climate change	High carbon stock areas	Percentage of Biomass from High Carbon Stock Land (PB-HCSL)	Land use change	Percentage of biomass obtained from land with high carbon stock	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO)	%	All	All		Other	
Climate change	High carbon stock areas	Carbon Storage Variation (CSV)	Climate Change mitigation	Change in carbon stocks/ Carbon sequestration	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO)	kg CO ₂ eq	All	All		Other	
Climate change	High carbon stock areas	Zero Conversion High Carbon Stock Crop Supply Percentage (ZC-HCS CSP)	Forest quality	Percentage of crop supply, by mass, was grown on fields with zero conversion High Carbon Stock (HCS) forests	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO)	%	All	All		Other	
Climate change	High carbon stock areas	Biogenic carbon storage (BCS100)	Climate change	Measures the total amount of biogenic carbon stored, of a biobased product, over a period of 100 years assuming successive loops of product recycling	Biogenic carbon storage (Corona et al. 2022)	kg C	All	All		Other	
Air	Air quality	Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP)	Ozone depletion	Depletion of the stratospheric ozone layer protecting from hazardous ultraviolet radiation	Steady-state ODPs as in (WMO 2014 + integrations)	kg CFC-11 eq	All	All			
Air	Air quality	Impact on human health	Particulate matter	Impact on human health caused by particulate matter emissions and its precursors (e.g., sulfur and nitrogen oxides)	PM method recommended by UNEP (UNEP 2016) (Fantke et al. 2015)	Disease incidence	All	All			

Table 5 (cont.). Selection of environmental LCA indicators. (1) PEF Framework, (2) ILCD Handbook, (3) Life Cycle Initiative, (Other) From reference indicated in the Metrics/ Characterization model/Reference box.

Key area	Subarea	Indicator	Impact category	Description	Metrics/ Characterization model/Reference	Unit	Stage	Sector	1	2	3
Water	Water quality	Comparative Toxic Unit for ecosystems	Ecotoxicity, freshwater	Impact of toxic substances on freshwater ecosystems	USEtox model 2.1 (Fankte et al, 2017)	CTUe	All	All			
Water	Water quality	Fraction of nutrients reaching marine end compartment (N)	Eutrophication,	Eutrophication and potential impact on marine ecosystems caused by nitrogen emissions mainly due to fertilizers, combustion, sewage	EUTREND model (Struijs et al, 2009) as implemented in ReCiPe	kg N eq	All	All			
Water	Water depletion	Weighted user deprivation potential	Water use	Depletion of available water depending on local water scarcity and water needs for human activities and ecosystem integrity	Available Water Remaining (AWARE)	m ³ world eq	All	All			
Soil Water	Soil quality Water quality	Accumulated Exceedance ¹ (AE)	Acidification	Acidification from air, water, and soil emissions (primarily sulfur compounds) due to combustion processes in electricity generation, heating, and transport	Accumulated Exceedance (Seppälä et al. 2006, Posch et al, 2008)	mol H ⁺ eq	All	All			
Soil	Soil quality Soil depletion	Soil quality index	Land use	Transformation and use of land for agriculture, roads, housing, mining or other purposes. The impact can include loss of species, organic matter, soil, filtration capacity, permeability	Soil quality index based on LANCA (Beck et al. 2010 and Bos et al. 2016)	Dimensionless (pt)	Feedstock End of life	All			

¹AE that characterizes the change in critical load exceedance of the sensitive area in terrestrial and major freshwater ecosystems where acidifying substances are deposited.

Table 5 (cont.). Selection of environmental LCA indicators. (1) PEF Framework, (2) ILCD Handbook, (3) Life Cycle Initiative, (Other) From reference indicated in the Metrics/ Characterization model/Reference box.

Key area	Subarea	Indicator	Impact category	Description	Metrics/ Characterization model/Reference	Unit	Stage	Sector	1	2	3
Hazardous substances	Human toxicity	Comparative Toxic Unit for humans	Human toxicity, cancer effects	Impact on human health (cancer effects) caused by absorbing substances through the air, water, and soil. Direct effects of products on humans are not measured	USEtox model (Rosenbaum et al, 2008)	CTUh	All	All			
Hazardous substances	Human toxicity	Comparative Toxic Unit for humans	Human toxicity, non- cancer effects	Impact on human health (on-cancer effects) caused by absorbing substances through the air, water, and soil. Direct effects of products on humans are not measured	USEtox model (Rosenbaum et al, 2008)	CTUh	All	All			
Hazardous substances	Human toxicity	Human exposure efficiency relative to U235	Ionizing radiation, human health	Impact of exposure to ionizing radiations on human health	Human health effect model as developed by Dreicer et al. 1995 (Frischknecht et al, 2000)	kBq U ²³⁵ eq	All	All			
Natural resources	Abiotic resources	Abiotic resource depletion – ADP ultimate reserves	Resource use, minerals and metals	Depletion of non-renewable resources and deprivation for future generations	CML 2002 (Guinée et al., 2002) and van Oers et al. 2002	kg Sb eq	All	All			
Natural resources	Abiotic resources	Abiotic resource depletion, fossil fuels – ADP-fossil	Resource use, fossils	Depletion of non-renewable resources and deprivation for future generations	CML 2002 (Guinée et al., 2002) and van Oers et al. 2002	MJ	All	All			
Natural resources	Ecosystem services	Deficit of Soil Organic Matter (SOM) due to land use	Biotic Production Potential (BPP)	Capacity of ecosystems to produce biomass	Methodology developed by Brandão and Milà i Canals L 2013	Mg SOM year	All	All		Other	
Natural resources	Ecosystem services	Carbon flows change due to land use	Climate Regulation Potential (CRP)	Capacity of ecosystems to uptake carbon from air	Methodology developed by Müller-Wenk and Brandão 2010	kg C/m ² year	All	All		Other	

Table 5 (cont.). Selection of environmental LCA indicators. (1) PEF Framework, (2) ILCD Handbook, (3) Life Cycle Initiative, (Other) From reference indicated in the Metrics/ Characterization model/Reference box

Key area	Subarea	Indicator	Impact category	Description	Metrics/ Characterization model	Unit	Stage	Sector	1	2	3
Natural resources	Ecosystem services	Water regulation capacity	Freshwater Regulation Potential (FWRP)	Capacity of ecosystems to regulate peak flow and base flow of surface water	Methodology developed by Saad et al. 2013	dimensionless	All	All			Other
Natural resources	Ecosystem services	Ground water recharge rate	Freshwater Regulation Potential (FWRP)	Capacity of ecosystems to recharge ground water	Methodology developed by Saad et al. 2013	mm/year	All	All			Other
Natural resources	Ecosystem services	Erosion resistance	Erosion Regulation Potential (ERP)	Capacity of ecosystems to stabilise soil and to prevent sediment accumulation downstream	Methodology developed by Saad et al. 2013	ton/ha year	All	All			Other
Natural resources	Ecosystem services	Cation exchange capacity	Water Purification Potential (WPP)	Chemical, physical and mechanical capacity of ecosystems to clean a polluted suspension of water	Methodology developed by Saad et al. 2013	cmol _c /kg _{soil}	All	All			Other
Biodiversity	Ecosystem diversity	Potential species loss	Land use	Transformation and use of land for agriculture, roads, housing, mining or other purposes. The impact can include loss of species, organic matter, soil, filtration capacity, permeability	Soil quality index based on LANCA (Beck et al. 2010 and Bos et al. 2016)	Dimensionless (pt)	Feedstock End of life	All			
Biodiversity	Ecosystem diversity	Potential species loss	Land use change	Percentage of biomass obtained from land with high carbon stock	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO)	%	All	All			Other

A total of 22 indicators were identified (Appendix C2), covering all the different key areas under the economic pillar. Indicators under profitability key area were predominantly used in the literature (Figure 10), reflecting the priority given to this key area by organizations in a growth-oriented market system (Arulnathan et al., 2022). This was followed by indicators under productivity key area, which are also a major focus of business. No LCA indicators were reported for the subareas *innovation and development*, *investment efficiency* and *external fundings* under *productivity*. Apart from the indicator “Minimum Feedstock Requirement”, which applies only to feedstock, the other indicators are suitable for all life cycle stages and bioeconomy sectors. After evaluating the identified indicators against the criteria outlined in Section 2.2, 8 economic indicators were selected, as it is presented in Table 6.

Figure 10. Distribution of economic LCA indicators by subarea.

Table 6. Economic LCA indicators selected.

Key area	Subarea	Indicator	Description	Metrics/Equation	Unit	Stage	Sector	Source
Profitability	Revenue	Share of raw material costs	Expresses the share of raw material costs in total production costs	Cost of raw materials/ production costs	€/€ (-)	All	All	(Wilting & Hanemaaijer, 2014)
Profitability	Revenue	Minimum Selling Price	The price of the raw material that results in the net present value is 0	-	€/t	All	All	(Koutinas et al., 2016)
Profitability	Revenue	Cost of manufacture to revenue ratio	-	Cost of manufacture/ overall revenue	€/€ (-)	All	All	(Jenkins 2022)
Long-term investment	Capital investment	Optimum Plant Capacity	The capacity that minimizes production cost	-	t/year	All	All	(Ioannidou et al., 2022)
Productivity	Material & energy-related	Turnover ratio	Gross annual sales/ fixed capital investment	Gross annual sales/ fixed capital investment	€/€ (-)	All	All	(Ruiz-Mercado et al., 2011)
Productivity	Human-related	Labor productivity	The efficiency of labor in producing economic output	Units of economic output/ work unit	€/number of employees (or working hours)	All	All	(Arulnathan et al., 2022)
Economic risks	Minimization of economic risks	Return on Investment (ROI)	Indicates how much economic benefit is derived from an investment in relation to its costs	(Revenue - Cost of investment)/ Cost of investment	%	All	All	(Peters et al., 2003)
Economic risks	Minimization of economic risks	Payback period (PBP)	Payback period is defined as the number of years required to recover the original cash investment	Fixed capital investment/ Average annual cash flow	years	All	All	(Peters et al., 2003)

Concerning the identification of social LCA indicators, it was observed that several scientific articles did not provide measurable indicators and also that authors referred to social subcategories as indicators (e.g., child labor). Similarly, the use of databases such as PSILCA (Product Social Impact Life Cycle Assessment database) and social hotspots (SHDB) was observed, from which authors also did not provide the specific sample of indicators applied.

After analyzing all the articles (Appendix B2), a total of 942 indicators were collected, from which those that were mistakenly reported as indicators were removed, obtaining a total of 702 indicators. Subsequently, a new screening focused on the identification of repeated indicators was performed, reducing the sample to 571 indicators (Appendix C3). Most of the indicators identified addressed social issues related to workers and the local community (47 % and 41 %, respectively), while indicators assessing issues related to consumers, society and value chain actors were a minority (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Distribution of social LCA indicators per key area.

In terms of the most frequently raised issues, occupational health and safety, working conditions, equal opportunities/discrimination received notable attention under the workers key area (Figure 12). In addition, access to resources and the health and safety of local communities were more frequently reported in relation to the local community key area. Compared to the environmental and economic pillars, the social aspect displayed more indicators (942 compared to 56 and 22 for the environmental and economic pillars). This is because the search for social indicators was broad in scope. In contrast, in the long-established fields of environment and economics, only a reduced compendium of highly relevant documents was analyzed, as substantial attempts have already been undertaken in these areas to standardize methodology and build a mutually agreed set of indicators.

Figure 12. Distribution of social LCA indicators per subarea.

Social LCA indicators selected

From the 571 indicators, 101 were selected for further use in the STAR4BBS project according to the criteria described in section 2.2, and complemented with indicators suggested by the UNEP-SETAC Life Cycle Initiative guidelines (2020) for those subareas for which no suitable indicators could be found in the literature, resulting in 15 additional indicators. Table 7 shows the full list of LCA indicators selected for the social pillar.

Table 7. Life cycle indicators selected in the social pillar.

Key area	Subarea	Indicator	Type	Unit	Stage	Sector	Reference
Consumers	Health and safety of end users	Quality of or number of information/signs on product health and safety	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Consumers	Health and safety of end users	total number of incidents of non-compliance with regulations and voluntary codes concerning health and safety impacts of products and services and type of outcomes	Quantitative	#	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Consumers	Health and safety of end users	Presence of labels on health and safety	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Consumers	Health and safety of end users	number of consumer complaints	Quantitative	#	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Consumers	Feedback mechanisms	Presence of a mechanism for customers to provide feedback	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Consumers	Feedback mechanisms	Management measures to improve feedback mechanisms	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Consumers	Transparency	Compliance with regulations regarding transparency	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Consumers	Transparency	Presence of clear information provided to consumers on end-of-life	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Consumers	Health and safety of end users	Tests performed to check safety	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Imbert et al., 2020)
Consumers	Product benefits	Products from natural source	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Imbert et al., 2020)
Consumers	Transparency	Available certification or documentation about sustainability issues	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Imbert et al., 2020)
Consumers	Feedback mechanisms	Level of customers satisfaction	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Foglia et al., 2021)
Consumers	Product benefits	Consumer savings	Quantitative	country money	All	All	(Masilela et al., 2021)
Local community	Health and safety	Organization's efforts to strengthen community health (e.g., through shared community access to organization health resources)	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)

Table 7 (cont.). Life cycle indicators selected in the social pillar.

Key area	Subarea	Indicator	Type	Unit	Stage	Sector	Reference
Local community	Contribution to economic development	Amount invested in community investment projects (e.g., CSR) (percent of annual revenue) and qualitative description of investments including any projects specific for women	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Local community	Food security	Perceived change in availability of food after the beginning of bio-energy operations	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Local community	Food security	Land that has been converted from staple crops	Quantitative	Ha	Feedstock	Agriculture	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Local community	Contribution to employment	Strength of policies on local hiring preferences	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Local community	Contribution to economic development	Percentage of spending on locally based suppliers	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Local community	Contribution to employment	Ratio of employment from local area/outside local area per category of employment	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Local community	Community engagement	Diversity of community stakeholder groups that engage with the organization	Qualitative/Semi-Quantitative	yes/no	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Local community	Respect of indigenous rights	Indigenous land rights conflicts/land claims	Qualitative	Yes/no	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Local community	Respect of indigenous rights	Strength of policies in place to protect the rights of indigenous community members	Qualitative	Yes/no	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Local community	Land use rights	Land prices	Quantitative	Country money	Feedstock	Agriculture	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Local community	Access to resources	Percentage of population (urban, rural, total) with access to improved sanitation facilities	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)

Table 7 (cont.). Life cycle indicators selected in the social pillar.

Key area	Subarea	Indicator	Type	Unit	Stage	Sector	Reference
Local community	Access to resources	Has the organization developed a project related infrastructure with mutual community access and benefit?	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Local community	Land use rights	Legal title of land right—has a legal title/concession for the land that is not challenged?	Qualitative	yes/no	Feedstock	Agriculture	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Local community	Land use rights	Percentage of farm owners having no conflict with land rights	Quantitative	%	Feedstock	Agriculture	(Prasara-A et al., 2019)
Local community	Contribution to economic development	Investments with direct benefit for local community	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Cadena et al., 2019)
Local community	Access to resources	Access to Improved Drinking Water	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Takeda et al., 2019)
Local community	Food security	Edible feedstock diverted from food chain to bio-based materials	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Imbert et al., 2020)
Local community	Secure living conditions	Endangerment of organization for the local community's secure living condition	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Nubi et al., 2021)
Local community	Community engagement	Communication channel between community and facility	Qualitative	yes/no	Feedstock	Agriculture	(Subramanian et al., 2021)
Local community	Migration	Number of individuals who resettle (voluntarily and involuntarily) that can be attributed to the organization	Quantitative	#	All	All	(UNEP, 2021)
Local community	Culture heritage	Evidence of policies/management plan(s) in place to protect and/or support cultural heritage	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(UNEP, 2021)
Local community	Culture heritage	Presence of organizational program to include cultural heritage expression in product design/ production	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(UNEP, 2021)
Local community	Culture heritage	Presence of relevant organizational information to community members in their spoken language(s)	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(UNEP, 2021)

Table 7 (cont.). Life cycle indicators selected in the social pillar.

Key area	Subarea	Indicator	Type	Unit	Stage	Sector	Reference
Local community	Culture heritage	Presence of documented initiatives and activities oriented to support and promote cultural heritage (e.g., funding of cultural activities and events)	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(UNEP, 2021)
Value chain actors	Promoting social responsibility	Formalized commitment of the organization to prevent corruption, referring to recognized standards	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Value chain actors	Promoting social responsibility	Membership of an initiative that promotes social responsibility along the supply chain	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Value chain actors	Supplier relationships	Presence of explicit code of conduct that protect human rights of workers among suppliers	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Value chain actors	Supplier relationships	Presence of transparent reporting of stakeholder concerns and suggestions	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Tavakoli et al., 2020)
Value chain actors	Wealth distribution	Percentage of farm owners satisfied with net income	Quantitative	%	Feedstock	Agriculture	(Prasara-A et al., 2019)
Value chain actors	Fair competition in the market	Involvement of smallholders or small suppliers. Percentage of feedstock that originates from associates, smallholders, and out-growers	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Value chain actors	Respect of intellectual property rights	Organization's policy and practice	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(UNEP, 2021)
Value chain actors	Respect of intellectual property rights	Use of local intellectual property	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(UNEP, 2021)
Society	Contribution to economic development	Contribution of the product/service/organization to economic progress (e.g., annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person)	Quantitative	%	All	All	(UNEP, 2021)
Society	Technology development	Involvement in technology transfer program or projects	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(UNEP, 2021)

Table 7 (cont.). Life cycle indicators selected in the social pillar.

Key area	Subarea	Indicator	Type	Unit	Stage	Sector	Reference
Society	Technology development	Partnerships in research and development	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(UNEP, 2021)
Society	Poverty alleviation	The organization carries out a poverty alleviation program	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(UNEP, 2021)
Society	Poverty alleviation	Contingency planning measures, disaster, emergency management plan, training programs, and recovery/ restoration plans	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(UNEP, 2021)
Workers	Fair salary	Costs of the agricultural and industrial working hours	Quantitative	\$/h	Feedstock; Materials & Products	All	(Souza et al., 2018)
Workers	Occupational health and safety	Sick-leave days per year per employee	Quantitative	number	All	All	(Siebert et al., 2018)
Workers	Working conditions	Compensation measures (e.g., exclusively payment, payment and free-time, exclusively free-time, any)	Qualitative	category	All	All	(Siebert et al., 2018)
Workers	Working conditions	Access to flexible working time agreements (e.g., working time accounts etc.)	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Siebert et al., 2018)
Workers	Working conditions	Percentage of employees participated in training per total employees	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Siebert et al., 2018)
Workers	Working conditions	Percentage of trainees per total employees	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Siebert et al., 2018)
Workers	Working conditions	Percentage of trainees employed permanently per total trainees	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Siebert et al., 2018)
Workers	Equal opportunities/ Discrimination	Percentage of female employees in management positions in relation to all employees in management positions	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Siebert et al., 2018)
Workers	Social benefits/social security	Measures for family support (e.g., support for childcare, support for female employees)	Qualitative	category	All	All	(Siebert et al., 2018)
Workers	Working conditions	Measures for older employees (e.g., offer of part-time contracts, special equipment of the workplace)	Qualitative	category	All	All	(Siebert et al., 2018)

Table 7 (cont.). Life cycle indicators selected in the social pillar.

Key area	Subarea	Indicator	Type	Unit	Stage	Sector	Reference
Workers	Equal opportunities/ Discrimination	Percentage of disabled employees per total employees	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Siebert et al., 2018)
Workers	Equal opportunities/ Discrimination	Percentage of foreign employees per total employees	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Siebert et al., 2018)
Workers	Freedom of association and collective bargaining	Existence of works' councils in the organization	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Siebert et al., 2018)
Workers	Occupational health and safety	Noise exposure	Quantitative	decibels	All	All	(Mattila et al., 2018)
Workers	Occupational health and safety	Number of injuries per level of employees.	Quantitative	#	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Workers	Occupational health and safety	Presence of a formal policy concerning health and safety	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Workers	Occupational health and safety	Preventative measures and emergency protocols exist regarding accidents and injuries	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Workers	Occupational health and safety	Preventative measures and emergency protocols exist regarding SVHC exposure	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Workers	Occupational health and safety	number of serious/non-serious Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) violations reported within the past three years and status of violations	Quantitative	#	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Workers	Occupational health and safety	Number of non-fatal accidents at work; fatal accidents at work	Quantitative	#	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Workers	Occupational health and safety	Percentage of workers that use appropriate personal protective equipment.	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Workers	Occupational health and safety	OSH training: Percentage of employees that have received OSH (Occupational Safety and Health) training	Quantitative	#	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)

Table 7 (cont.). Life cycle indicators selected in the social pillar.

Key area	Subarea	Indicator	Type	Unit	Stage	Sector	Reference
Workers	Freedom of association and collective bargaining	Evidence of restriction to freedom of association and collective bargaining	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Workers	Freedom of association and collective bargaining	presence of unions within the organization is adequately supported	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Workers	Child labor	Absence of working children under the legal age or 15 years old	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Workers	Working conditions	Excessive hours of work	Quantitative	hours	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Workers	Working conditions	Number of holidays effectively used by employees	Quantitative	#	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Workers	Working conditions	Clear communication of working hours and overtime arrangements	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Workers	Social benefits/social security	Employments benefits (e.g., housing, health care, holidays) provided by operations	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Workers	Equal opportunities/Discrimination	Presence of formal policies on equal opportunities	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Workers	Equal opportunities/Discrimination	total numbers of incidents of discrimination and actions taken	Quantitative	#	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Workers	Equal opportunities/Discrimination	ratio of basic salary of men to women by employee category	Quantitative	dimensionless	All	All	(Falcone et al., 2018)
Workers	Occupational health and safety	Number/percentage of injuries, illness and fatal accidents in the organization by job qualification inside the company	Quantitative	# or %	All	All	(Contreras-Lisperguer et al., 2018)

Table 7 (cont.). Life cycle indicators selected in the social pillar.

Key area	Subarea	Indicator	Type	Unit	Stage	Sector	Reference
Workers	Fair salary	Lowest paid workers, compared to the country's minimum wage (Working Conditions)	Quantitative	country money	All	All	(Contreras-Lisperguer et al., 2018)
Workers	Forced labor	Workers voluntarily agree on employment terms	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Contreras-Lisperguer et al., 2018)
Workers	Employment relationship	Employment contracts stipulate wage, working time, holidays and terms of resignation	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Shemfe et al., 2018)
Workers	Employment relationship	Employment contracts are comprehensible to workers and kept on file	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Chaderi et al., 2018)
Workers	Fair salary	Percentage of workers satisfied with wage	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Prasara-A et al., 2019)
Workers	Working conditions	Percentage of workers reporting having at least 1 day off a week	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Prasara-A et al., 2019)
Workers	Working conditions	Percentage of workers reporting working hours aligned with regulations	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Prasara-A et al., 2019)
Workers	Working conditions	Percentage of workers reporting overtime work payment is aligned with regulations	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Prasara-A et al., 2019)
Workers	Equal opportunities/ Discrimination	Percentage of workers reporting no discrimination at work	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Prasara-A et al., 2019)
Workers	Forced labor	Percentage of workers reporting no forced labor	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Prasara-A et al., 2019)
Workers	Occupational health and safety	Sites with OHSAS certification	Quantitative	# or %	All	All	(Cadena et al., 2019)
Workers	Social benefits/social security	Expenditures in social security and pension funds	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Cadena et al., 2019)
Workers	Working conditions	Training hours	Quantitative	hours	All	All	(Cadena et al., 2019)

Table 7 (cont.). Life cycle indicators selected in the social pillar.

Key area	Subarea	Indicator	Type	Unit	Stage	Sector	Reference
Workers	Equal opportunities/ Discrimination	Code of conduct training ratio	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Cadena et al., 2019)
Workers	Equal opportunities/ Discrimination	Average employee's age	Quantitative	#	All	All	(Cadena et al., 2019)
Workers	Equal opportunities/ Discrimination	Local/indigenous Workers Rate	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Cadena et al., 2019)
Workers	Fair salary	Year of last minimum wage update	Quantitative	year	All	All	(Takeda et al., 2019)
Workers	Employment relationship	Percentage of workers who have written agreements with their employers that meet at least national and international labor treaties including social security	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Sawaengsak et al., 2019)
Workers	Forced labor	Percentage of workers who have the freedom of movement, such as free from curfews or lock-ins	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Sawaengsak et al., 2019)
Workers	Forced labor	Percentage of workers who are not forced to work overtime	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Sawaengsak et al., 2019)
Workers	Freedom of association and collective bargaining	Percentage of workers who have a freedom to negotiate as individuals or as groups or through a union or representatives of their choosing to negotiate the terms of their employment	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Sawaengsak et al., 2019)
Workers	Occupational health and safety	Percentage of workers who have been provided a first aid kit when the emergency event occurs	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Sawaengsak et al., 2019)
Workers	Employment relationship	Rate of part-time employees	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Bezama et al., 2021)
Workers	Employment relationship	Rate of fixed-term employees	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Bezama et al., 2021)
Workers	Employment relationship	Rate of employees provided by temporary work agencies	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Bezama et al., 2021)
Workers	Equal opportunities/ Discrimination	Rate of female employees	Quantitative	%	All	All	(Bezama et al., 2021)
Workers	Fair salary	Capital participation	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Zeug et al., 2021)
Workers	Fair salary	Profit-sharing and bonuses	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Zeug et al., 2021)

Table 7 (cont.). Life cycle indicators selected in the social pillar.

Key area	Subarea	Indicator	Type	Unit	Stage	Sector	Reference
Workers	Equal opportunities/ Discrimination	Measures to improve gender equality	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(Zeug et al., 2021)
Workers	Mental or physical abuse	Number of sexual harassment incidents reported on a grievance helpline	Quantitative	#	All	All	(UNEP, 2021)
Workers	Mental or physical abuse	Existence of clear responsibilities for matters of sexual harassment within the organization	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(UNEP, 2021)
Workers	Mental or physical abuse	Efforts by the organization to reduce the risk of sexual harassment	Qualitative	yes/no	All	All	(UNEP, 2021)

5 Case studies

To increase the relevance and applicability of D3.1, this report also includes some recent research reports that have applied LCA methodology and circularity analysis to different sectors of the bioeconomy. A total of 30 research articles covering the environmental, social and economic pillars of sustainability, as well as circularity assessments, were analyzed (see Annex). In line with the collection of indicators, the environmental pillar is the most developed in the literature according to the LCA methodology, with climate change and natural resources as the most outstanding impact indicators in the assessments. This is attributed to the application of the standardized methodology (ISO 14040), which has been used as a tool to assess the sustainable potential of bio-based production models within the bioeconomy sectors. It should be noted that all key areas identified in this report are assessed in the literature using LCA indicators, which also increases and improves the relevance and appropriateness of the selection and ranking considered.

On the other hand, although more social indicators have been identified for assessing social sustainability, there are not many research articles in the literature that develop this type of analysis. The potential reasons for this include: (1) it is difficult to collect social data (questionnaires/survey need to be developed with meaningful stakeholder and societal participation) and (2) there is no standardized methodology for social analysis. However, as observed for the environmental pillar, indicators and analyses have been found in the literature for all the key areas identified in this D3.1, with the areas of consumers, local community and society standing out.

For the economic pillar, techno-economic assessments are the most developed type of analysis in the literature, usually combined with life cycle environmental assessments. Although all key areas were found to be represented in the manuscripts reviewed, long-term profitability and investment indicators stand out, as well as those more related to financial metrics, which are essential to identify the economic viability of a production process or value chain.

Circularity analysis had the fewest examples in the literature (some other examples were found for the bioenergy sector, but as this is not one of the sectors covered by the STAR4BBS project, these articles were not included in the review). The key areas considered in a higher number of reports are "production process" and "product and material design". A potential reason for the lower number of reports with the circularity-based analyses could be that this is a more recent type of assessment in comparison to those related to environmental and social sustainability. However, it has also been possible to identify the analysis of all the key areas proposed in this deliverable.

Finally, as far as the bioeconomy sector is concerned, *agriculture and forestry*, *bio-based chemicals and pharmaceuticals*, and *plastics and rubber* are by far the sectors with the highest number of research articles in the literature.

6 Conclusions

Sustainability indicators are an integral part of the monitoring system that STAR4BBS aims to develop to monitor and assess the robustness and effectiveness of sustainability certification schemes and labels, promoting, at the same time, a greater harmonization within the bioeconomy. This report focuses specifically on screening sustainability indicators from a life-cycle perspective, covering the three dimensions of sustainability: environmental, economic, and social. After an analysis of different documents (scientific publications, guidelines, and databases), a total of 44 environmental, 22 economic and 571 social LCA indicators were identified. From these, a careful selection was made of those that were relevant to the project, measurable, robust and reliable. The selected indicators, consisting of 16 environmental, 8 economic and 101 social indicators, will be used to assess the sustainability of the value chain case studies in further activities of the project, taking into account the availability of data and sector specificities. Although the environmental dimension is the most developed and commonly assessed in LCA, also attested by the performed literature review, this report underlines the importance of a holistic approach that allows for a comprehensive analysis of the synergies and trade-offs that may exist between the three dimensions of sustainability.

7 Appendix

A.1. Materials from second co-creation workshop: MIRO board displaying the responses from attendees

Environmental pillar

Circularity pillar

How do you differentiate between circularity and environmental indicators? Aren't all circular indicators also covering environmental aspects?

This whole principle seems to be underdeveloped compared to the others. There are many more criteria and indicators possible for circularity...

Economic pillar

A.2. Materials of the consultation activity among STAR4BBS partners

CONSULTATION ACTIVITY:

IDENTIFICATION OF RELEVANT INDICATORS ON THE BASIS OF THE PRIORITIZED POLICY OBJECTIVES

1. Introduction

The activity asked participants (e.g., members of STAR4BBS consortium) to select the categories or subcategories of indicators they considered related to the policy targets by placing a star next to the category or subcategory. It was allowed to select more than one category or subcategory. Figure 1 presents the appearance that the consultation activity had for each policy target in the Miro dashboard. There were two types of stars:

- Black stars. They meant a positive relation (e.g., indicators of the category or subcategory contributed to achieve the policy target, or indicators were improved by the achievement of the policy target).
- Red stars. They meant a negative relation (e.g., there was a trade-off between the policy target and the category or subcategory).

Figure 1. Layout of consultation activity in the Miro dashboard for each policy target.

Participants were also given the opportunity to leave comments on post-its if they wanted to elaborate on a point.

The aim of this consultation was two-fold:

1. Identifying which categories or subcategories of indicators are relevant towards achieving policy targets.
2. Determining if there are missing policy objectives that address important categories or subcategories.

A total of 14 policy targets were analyzed in the activity based on the results of WP1 (Task 1.1):

1. By 2030, at least 20% of the carbon used in chemicals and plastic products should come from sustainable non-fossil sources.
2. Reach a 55% reduction in GHG emissions by 2030.
3. At least 45% of the energy in the EU comes from renewable sources by 2030.
4. Reach climate neutrality by 2050.
5. Reduce the overall use and risk of chemical pesticides by 50% by 2030.
6. Reduce the use of fertilizers by at least 20% by 2030.
7. By 2050, 5% of the energy used in aviation should come from advanced biofuels.
8. Increase the sustainability of products in the EU starting from its design/inception and ensure the sustainability of renewable bio-based materials.
9. Establish a product performance on energy use and efficiency, recyclability and environmental impact.
10. Ensure the sustainability of renewable bio-based materials.
11. Make sustainable management of soils the norm across the EU.
12. Set out conditions to ensure that the environmental impact of the production and consumption of bio-based, biodegradable and compostable plastics is positive.
13. Provide definitions and criteria to determine which economic activities are environmentally sustainable.
14. Introduce sustainability criteria for biomass and biogas.

2.

Results

Tables 1 and 2 display the frequency of black star ratings (indicating a positive relation) given to each pillar for the quantitative and qualitative policy targets, respectively. The environmental pillar was by far the most frequently perceived as positively related, irrespective of the policy objectives considered. In addition, Table 3 shows a qualitative summary of the categories and subcategories that were considered related to the policy objectives with at least one star. In this occasion, both positive and negative relationships are illustrated using a three-pattern color to differentiate the three possible scenarios. The green color represents a positive relationship (e.g., the category/subcategory obtained at least one black star and no red stars), the red color a negative relationship (e.g., the category/subcategory obtained at least one red star and no black stars) and the cells in yellow are those in which both a positive and negative relationship was identified (e.g., the category/subcategory obtained at least one red star and one black star). The answers given by the participants in the Miro dashboard are collected in the Annex section for the 14 policy objectives.

Table 1. Frequency of black stars ratings (indicating a positive relation) obtained by each pillar for the quantitative targets.

	Targets	Pillar				
		Environmental	Social	Economic	Sustainable Governance	Circularity
1	By 2030, at least 20% of the carbon used in chemicals and plastic products should come from sustainable non-fossil sources	71%	6%	0%	0%	23%
2	Reach a 55% reduction in GHG emissions by 2030	79%	14%	0%	0%	7%
3	At least 45% of the energy in the EU comes from renewable sources by 2030	71%	24%	0%	0%	5%
4	Reach climate neutrality by 2050	82%	9%	0%	0%	9%
5	Reduce the overall use and risk of chemical pesticides by 50% by 2030	97%	3%	0%	0%	0%
6	Reduce the use of fossil-based fertilizers by at least 20% by 2030	95%	5%	0%	0%	0%
7	By 2050, 5% of the energy used in aviation should come from ad-vanced biofuels.	95%	5%	0%	0%	0%

Table 2. Frequency of black stars ratings (indicating a positive relation) obtained by each pillar for the qualitative targets.

		Pillar				
		Environmental	Social	Economic	Sustainable Governance	Circularity
8	Increase the sustainability of products in the EU starting from its design/inception and ensure the sustainability of renewable bio-based materials	52%	14%	1%	9%	23%
9	Establish a product performance on energy use and efficiency, recyclability and environmental impact.	69%	8%	0%	0%	23%
10	Ensure the sustainability of renewable bio-based materials	57%	15%	11%	0%	17%
11	Make sustainable management of soils the norm across the EU	94%	3%	0%	0%	3%
12	Set out conditions to ensure that the environmental impact of the production and consumption of bio-based, biodegradable and compostable plastics is positive.	76%	4%	0%	0%	20%
13	Provide definitions and criteria to determine which economic activities are environmentally sustainable	47%	8%	22%	13%	9%
14	Introduce sustainability criteria for biomass and biogas	56%	14%	10%	12%	8%

Table 3. Qualitative summary of the categories and subcategories that were considered related to the 14 policy objectives.

Pillar	Category	Subcategory	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
Environmental	Air	Climate change														
Environmental	Air	Air quality														
Environmental	Water	Water quality														
Environmental	Water	Water depletion														
Environmental	Soil	Soil quality														
Environmental	Soil	Soil depletion														
Environmental	Toxicity	Toxicity														
Environmental	Natural resources	Abiotic resources														
Environmental	Natural resources	Biotic resources														
Environmental	Natural resources	Land use														
Environmental	Natural resources	Ecosystem services														
Environmental	Biodiversity	Biodiversity														
Environmental	Best practices	Chemical management														
Environmental	Best practices	Waste management														
Environmental	Best practices	Animal welfare														
Environmental	Best practices	Biosafety/ Biosecurity														
Environmental	Best practices	Others														
Social	Workers															
Social	Local community															
Social	Society															
Social	Consumers															
Social	Value chain actors															
Economic	Profitability															
Economic	Productivity															
Economic	Business diversity															
Economic	Consumer															
Economic	Long-term investment															
Sustainable Governance	Management															
Sustainable Governance	Internal engagement															
Sustainable Governance	Leadership															
Sustainable Governance	Materiality															
Sustainable Governance	Customer engagement															
Sustainable Governance	Reporting															
Circularity	Resource-efficiency															
Circularity	EoL															
Circularity	Eco-design															
Circularity	Business model															

Green color: positive relationship (e.g., the category/subcategory obtained at least one black star and no red stars); red color: negative relationship (e.g., the category/subcategory obtained at least one red star and no black stars); yellow color: positive and negative relationship (e.g., the category/subcategory obtained at least one red star and one black star). (1) By 2030, at least 20% of the carbon used in chemicals and plastic products should come from sustainable non-fossil sources; (2) Reach a 55% reduction in GHG emissions by 2030; (3) At least 45% of the energy in the EU comes from renewable sources by 2030; (4) Reach climate neutrality by 2050; (5) Reduce the overall use and risk of chemical pesticides by 50% by 2030; (6) Reduce the use of fertilizers by at least 20% by 2030; (7) By 2050, 5% of the energy used in aviation should come from advanced biofuels; (8) Increase the sustainability of products in the EU starting from its design/inception and ensure the sustainability of renewable bio-based materials; (9) Establish a product performance on energy use and efficiency, recyclability and environmental impact; (10) Ensure the sustainability of renewable bio-based materials; (11) Make sustainable management of soils the norm across the EU; (12) Set out conditions to ensure that the environmental impact of the production and consumption of bio-based, biodegradable and compostable plastics is positive; (13) Provide definitions and criteria to determine which economic activities are environmentally sustainable; (14) Introduce sustainability criteria for biomass and biogas.

3. Annex A. Material from the consultation activity extracted from Miro's dashboard.

Which categories/subcategories of indicators you think are related to the policy targets?

- ★ Postivite relationship
- ★ Trade-offs

miro

Target 1. By 2030, at least 20% of the carbon used in chemicals and plastic products should come from sustainable non-fossil sources.

Target 2. Reach a 55% reduction in GHG emissions by 2030

Target 3. At least 45% of the energy in the EU comes from renewable sources by 2030

Target 4. Reach climate neutrality by 2050

Target 5. Reduce the overall use and risk of chemical pesticides by 50% by 2030

Target 6. Reduce the use of fossil-based fertilizers by at least 20% by 2030

Target 7. By 2050, 5% of the energy used in aviation should come from advanced biofuels.

Target 8. Increase the sustainability of products in the EU starting from its design/inception and ensure the sustainability of renewable bio-based materials

Target 9. Establish a product performance on energy use and efficiency, recyclability and environmental impact.

Target 10. Ensure the sustainability of renewable bio-based materials

Target 11. Make sustainable management of soils the norm across the EU

Target 12. Set out conditions to ensure that the environmental impact of the production and consumption of bio-based, biodegradable and compostable plastics is positive.

Target 13. Provide definitions and criteria to determine which economic activities are environmentally sustainable

Target 14. Introduce sustainability criteria for biomass and biogas.

B.1. Sample of articles that were analyzed in the search for economic LCA indicators.

Table B1. Sample of scientific publications analyzed.

Title	First author	Year	DOI
Key performance indicators for energy management in the Swedish pulp and paper industry.	Andersson	2019	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2019.03.004
Economic Indicators for Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment: Going beyond Life Cycle Costing.	Arulnathan	2022	http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/su15010013
Indicators of Sustainable Development for Industry: A General Framework, Process Safety and Environmental Protection.	Azapagic	2000	https://doi.org/10.1205/095758200530763
Techno-economic risk assessment, life cycle analysis and life cycle costing for poly(butylene succinate) and poly(lactic acid) production using renewable resources.	Ioannidou	2022	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.150594
Essential Manufacturing Metrics and KPIs to Guide Your Industrial Transformation.	Jenkins	2022	https://www.netsuite.com/portal/resource/articles/erp/manufacturing-kpis-metrics.shtml
Techno-economic evaluation of a complete bioprocess for 2,3-butanediol production from renewable resources.	Koutinas	2016	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2015.12.005
General indicator for techno-economic assessment of renewable energy resources	Liu	2018	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2017.11.054
Plant design and economics for chemical engineers	Peters	2003	ISBN-9780070664739
Sustainability indicators for chemical processes: II.	Ruiz-Mercado	2012	https://doi.org/10.1021/ie200755k

Table B1 (cont.). Sample of scientific publications analyzed.

Title	First author	Year	DOI
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Share of raw material costs in total production costs	Wilting	2014	https://www.pbl.nl/sites/default/files/downloads/pbl-2014-share-of-raw-material-costs-in-total-production-costs_01506.pdf
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B2. Sample of articles that were analyzed in the search for social LCA indicators.

Table B2. Sample of scientific publications analyzed.

Title	First author	Year	DOI
Social life cycle assessment of palm oil biodiesel: a case study in Jambi Province of Indonesia	Manik	2013	https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-013-0581-5
Screening potential social impacts of fossil fuels and biofuels for vehicles	Ekener-Petersen	2014	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2014.05.034
Social dimensions of energy supply alternatives in steelmaking: comparison of biomass and coal production scenarios in Australia	Weldegiorgis	2014	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2013.09.056
Prioritization of bioethanol production pathways in China based on life cycle sustainability assessment and multicriteria decision-making	Ren	2015	https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-015-0877-8
Customized scoring and weighting approaches for quantifying and aggregating results in social life cycle impact assessment	do Carmo	2017	https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-017-1280-4
Addressing uncertain scoring and weighting factors in social life cycle assessment	do Carmo	2017	https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-017-1275-1

Table B2 (cont.). Sample of scientific publications analyzed.

Title	First author	Year	DOI
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Social life cycle assessment of first and second-generation ethanol production technologies in Brazil	Souza	2018	https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-016-1112-y
Testing environmental and social indicators for biorefineries: bioethanol and biochemical production	Valente	2018	https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-017-1331-x
Social life cycle assessment: in pursuit of a framework for assessing wood-based products from bioeconomy regions in Germany	Siebert	2018	https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-016-1066-0
Social life cycle assessment indices and indicators to monitor the social implications of wood-based products	Siebert	2018	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.02.146
Evaluating social sustainability of bioeconomy value chains through integrated use of local and global methods	Mattila	2018	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2017.12.019
Social Life Cycle Approach as a Tool for Promoting the Market Uptake of Bio-Based Products from a Consumer Perspective	Falcone	2018	https://doi.org/10.3390/su10041031
Financial modelling strategies for social life cycle assessment: A project appraisal of biodiesel production and sustainability in Newfoundland and Labrador, Canada	Sajid	2018	https://doi.org/10.3390/su10093289
Developing Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment methodology by applying values-based sustainability weighting - Tested on biomass based and fossil transportation fuels	Ekener	2018	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.01.211
Addressing positive impacts in social LCA— discussing current and new approaches exemplified by the case of vehicle fuels	Ekener	2018	https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-016-1058-0

Table B2 (cont.). Sample of scientific publications analyzed.

Title	First author	Year	DOI
Sustainability assessment of electricity cogeneration from sugarcane bagasse in Jamaica	Contreras-Lisperguer	2018	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.07.322
Social hotspot analysis and trade policy implications of the use of bioelectrochemical systems for resource recovery from wastewater	Shemfe	2018	https://doi.org/10.3390/su10093193
A multi-objective robust possibilistic programming approach to sustainable switchgrass-based bioethanol supply chain network design	Ghaderi	2018	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.12.218
Environmental and social life cycle assessment to enhance sustainability of sugarcane-based products in Thailand	Prasara-A	2019	https://doi.org/10.1007/s10098-019-01715-y
Social life cycle assessment methodology for evaluating production process design: Biorefinery case study	Cadena	2019	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.117718
Novel macroalgae (seaweed) biorefinery systems for integrated chemical, protein, salt, nutrient and mineral extractions and environmental protection by green synthesis and life cycle sustainability assessments	Sadhukhan	2019	https://doi.org/10.1039/C9GC00607A
Are renewables as friendly to humans as to the environment? A social life cycle assessment of renewable electricity	Takeda	2019	https://doi.org/10.3390/su11051370
Development of a social impact assessment method and application to a case study of sugarcane, sugar, and ethanol in Thailand	Sawaengsak	2019	https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-019-01624-8
Life cycle sustainability assessment in the energy sector	Stamford	2019	https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-815581-3.00005-1
Social life cycle assessment for industrial biotechnology	Macombe	2019	https://doi.org/10.1007/10_2019_99

Table B2 (cont.). Sample of scientific publications analyzed.

Title	First author	Year	DOI
Blended Lifecycle Integrated Social System Method	Tavakoli	2020	https://doi.org/10.1007/s41742-020-00284-z
Chapter 6: Social Assessment	Imbert	2020	https://doi.org/10.1039/9781839160271-00166
A protocol for the definition of supply chains in product social life cycle assessment: application to bioelectricity	Martín-Gamboa	2020	https://doi.org/10.1039/D0SE00919A
Costructural law, exergy analysis and life cycle energy sustainability assessment: an expanded framework applied to a boiler	Guarino	2020	https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-020-01779-9
A data-driven approach for supply chain network design under uncertainty with consideration of social concerns	Fattahi	2020	https://doi.org/10.1007/s10479-020-03532-9
Social sustainability of treatment technologies for bioenergy generation from the municipal solid waste using best worst method	Alidoosti	2021	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.125592
Integrating regionalized socioeconomic considerations onto life cycle assessment for evaluating bioeconomy value chains: A case study on hybrid wood-concrete ceiling elements	Bezama	2021	https://doi.org/10.3390/su13084221
Sustainable supply chain planning for biomass-based power generation with environmental risk and supply uncertainty considerations: a real-life case study	Fattahi	2020	https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2020.1746427
Assessing socio-economic value of innovative materials recovery solutions validated in existing wastewater treatment plants	Foglia	2021	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.129048
Holistic approach in the evaluation of the sustainability of bio-based products: An Integrated Assessment Tool	Ladu	2021	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2021.07.006

Table B2 (cont.). Sample of scientific publications analyzed.

Title	First author	Year	DOI
A life cycle sustainability assessment of biomethane versus biohydrogen-For application in electricity or vehicle fuel? Case studies for African context	Masilela	2021	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.129567
A Prospective Social Life Cycle Assessment (sLCA) of Electricity Generation from Municipal Solid Waste in Nigeria	Nubi	2021	https://doi.org/10.3390/su131810177
Sustainability assessment of combined animal fodder and fuel production from microalgal biomass	Portner	2021	https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph182111351
The mathematics of life cycle sustainability assessment	Sadhukhan	2021	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.127457
A novel social life cycle assessment method for determining workers' human development: a case study of the sugarcane biorefineries in Brazil	Souza	2021	https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-021-01936-8
Capital-based life cycle sustainability assessment: Evaluation of potential industrial symbiosis synergies	Subramanian	2021	https://doi.org/10.1111/ijec.13135
A framework for implementing holistic and integrated life cycle sustainability assessment of regional bioeconomy	Zeug	2021	https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-021-01983-1
Environmental, social, and economic assessment of energy utilization of crop residue in China	Zhang	2021	https://doi.org/10.1007/s11708-020-0696-x

C.1. Full list of identified environmental LCA indicators

Excel file STAR4BBS_WP3_Environmental LCA indicator (additional material)

C.2. Full list of identified economic LCA indicators

Excel file STAR4BBS_WP3_Economic LCA indicators (additional material)

C.3. Full list of identified social LCA indicators

Excel file STAR4BBS_WP3_Social LCA indicators (additional material)

C.4. Sample of research reports performing LCA and circularity assessments for bioeconomy sectors

Excel file Case studies (additional material)

8 References

- Alejandre, E.M., Potts, S.G., Guinée, J.B., van Bodegom, P.M., 2022. Characterisation model approach for LCA to estimate land use impacts on pollinator abundance and illustrative characterisation factors. *J. Clean. Prod.* 346, 131043. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.131043>
- Alliance for Water Stewardship (AWS), 2022. AWS Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) Indicator Frameworks.
- Arias, A., Estévez-Rivadulla, S., Rebolledo-Leiva, R., Feijoo, G., González-García, S., & Moreira, M. T. (2024). Boosting the transition to biorefineries in compliance with sustainability and circularity criteria. *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering*, 12(5), 113361. [10.1016/j.jece.2024.113361](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2024.113361)
- Arias, A., Feijoo, G., & Moreira, M. T. (2023). Process modelling and environmental assessment on the valorization of lignocellulosic waste to antimicrobials. *Food and Bioproducts Processing*, 137, 113-123.
- Arias, A., Feijoo, G., & Moreira, M. T. (2024). Macroalgae as a sustainable biostimulant for crop production according to techno-economic and environmental criteria. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2024.05.019>
- Aziz, M. S. B., Mondol, M. M. R., Alam, M. M., Haque, M. M., & Islam, S. R. (2024). Underpinning the criteria for the sustainability assessment of Hakaluki Haor using the RAPFISH tool. *Fisheries Research*, 278, 107080. [10.1016/j.fishres.2024.107080](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2024.107080)
- Beylot, A., Ardente, F., Marques, A., Mathieux, F., Pant, R., Sala, S., Zampori, L., 2020. Abiotic and biotic resources impact categories in LCA: Development of new approaches - Accounting for abiotic resources dissipation and biotic resources. Luxembourg. <https://doi.org/10.2760/232839>
- Bosona, T. (2024). Life Cycle Assessment of Dried Organic Apple Value Chains Considering Conventional and Heat-Pump-Assisted Drying Processes: The Case of Sweden. *Agriculture*, 14(3), 461.
- Brandão, M., & i Canals, L. M., 2013. Global characterisation factors to assess land use impacts on biotic production. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 18, 1243-1252. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-012-0381-3>
- Brunet-Navarro, P., Jochheim, H., Cardellini, G., Richter, K., Muys, B., 2021. Climate mitigation by energy and material substitution of wood products has an expiry date. *J. Clean. Prod.* 303, 127026. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.127026>
- Ceballos-Santos, S., Entrena-Barbero, E., Laso, J., Margallo, M., González-García, S., Moreira, M. T., ... & Aldaco, R. (2024). Applying a water-energy-food nexus approach to seafood products from the European Atlantic area. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 442, 140804. [10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.140804](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.140804)
- Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU), 2023. CBE JU Annual Work Programme 2023. <https://doi.org/10.3776/tpre.2019.v9n2p91-93>
- Corona, B., Hoefnagels, R., Gürsel, I. V., Moretti, C., van Veen, M., & Junginger, M. (2022). Metrics for minimising environmental impacts while maximising circularity in

biobased products: The case of lignin-based asphalt. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 379, 134829. 10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.134829

Dankers, C., 2003. *Environmental and Social Standards, Certification and Labelling for Cash Crops*. Rome.

Dasgupta, D., Sidana, A., Ghosh, P., Sharma, T., Singh, J., Prabhune, A., ... & Ghosh, D. (2021). Energy and life cycle impact assessment for xylitol production from corncob. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 278, 123217. 10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.123217

De Laurentiis, V., Secchi, M., Bos, U., Horn, R., Laurent, A., Sala, S., 2019. Soil quality index: Exploring options for a comprehensive assessment of land use impacts in LCA. *J. Clean. Prod.* 215, 63–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.12.238>

Dekamin, M., Kheiralipour, K., & Afshar, R. K. (2022). Energy, economic, and environmental assessment of coriander seed production using material flow cost accounting and life cycle assessment. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 29(55), 83469-83482. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-21585-0>

Directorate-General for Environment, 2021. Environmental footprint methods [WWW Document]. Environ. Eur. Comm. URL https://environment.ec.europa.eu/news/environmental-footprint-methods-2021-12-16_en (accessed 2.2.23).

EFRA, 2022. ESRS E5 Resource use and circular economy.

Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2023a. Circular economy principles [WWW Document]. URL <https://ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/topics/circular-economy-introduction/overview#principles> (accessed 6.14.23).

Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2023b. Circular economy principles [WWW Document]. URL <https://ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/topics/circular-economy-introduction/overview#principles> (accessed 6.4.23).

Entrena-Barbero, E., Santos, S. C., Cortés, A., Esteve-Llorens, X., Moreira, M. T., Villanueva-Rey, P., ... & Feijoo, G. (2023). Methodological guidelines for the calculation of a Water-Energy-Food nexus index for seafood products. *Science of the Total Environment*, 877, 162845. 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.162845

European Commission, 2012. Indirect Land Use Change (ILUC) [WWW Document]. Press Corner. URL https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/MEMO_12_787 (accessed 6.5.23).

European Commission, 2013. 2013/179/EU: Commission Recommendation of 9 April 2013 on the use of common methods to measure and communicate the life cycle environmental performance of products and organisations Text with EEA relevance.

European Commission, 2018. *A new Bioeconomy strategy for a sustainable Europe: Restoring healthy ecosystems and enhancing biodiversity*.

European Commission, 2020. *A new Circular Economy Action Plan For a cleaner and more competitive Europe*. Brussels.

- European Commission, 2022a. Clean environment and zero pollution (HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION-01) [WWW Document]. Funding tender Oppor. URL <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-cl6-2021-zeropollution-01-06> (accessed 11.8.22).
- European Commission, 2022b. Clean environment and zero pollution (HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION-01) [WWW Document]. Funding tender Oppor. URL https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/zero-pollution-action-plan/zero-pollution-targets_en (accessed 11.15.22).
- European Commission, 2023a. About us [WWW Document]. Eur. Platf. LCA | EPLCA. URL <https://eplca.jrc.ec.europa.eu/aboutUs.html#menu1> (accessed 6.5.23).
- European Commission, 2023b. European Platform on Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) [WWW Document]. Environment. URL <https://ec.europa.eu/environment/ipp/lca.htm> (accessed 6.5.23).
- European Commission, 2023c. ILCD International Life Cycle Data system [WWW Document]. Eur. Platf. LCA | EPLCA. URL <https://eplca.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ilcd.html> (accessed 6.5.23).
- European Commission, 2023d. Life-cycle costing [WWW Document]. Green Bus. URL [https://green-business.ec.europa.eu/green-public-procurement/life-cycle-costing_en#:~:text=Life-cycle costing \(LCC\) means considering all the costs,the product%2C work or service](https://green-business.ec.europa.eu/green-public-procurement/life-cycle-costing_en#:~:text=Life-cycle costing (LCC) means considering all the costs,the product%2C work or service)
- European Commission, J.R.C., 2012. Characterisation factors of the ILCD Recommended Life Cycle Impact Assessment methods, Insitute of Environment and Sustainability. <https://doi.org/10.2788/60825>
- European Environment Agency (EEA), 2016a. Circular economy in Europe - developing the knowledge base, Publication Office of the Euopean Union.
- European Environment Agency (EEA), 2016b. Circular economy in Europe - developing the knowledge base, Publication Office of the Euopean Union.
- European Environment Agency (EEA), 2023. Term: non-renewable resource [WWW Document]. EEA Gloss. URL <https://www.eea.europa.eu/help/glossary/eea-glossary/non-renewable-resource> (accessed 4.21.23).
- European Parliament, 2023. Commission 2014-19 New boost for jobs, growth and investment STRATEGY for SECONDARY RAW MATERIALS STRATEGY for SECONDARY RAW MATERIALS [WWW Document]. Legis. Train Sched. URL <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/theme-new-boost-for-jobs-growth-and-investment/file-strategy-for-secondary-raw-materials> (accessed 4.21.23).
- FAO, 2019. Indicators to monitor and evaluate the sustainability of bioeconomy - overview of a proposed way forward. FAO, Rome.
- Fernández-Lobato, L., Ruiz-Carrasco, B., Tostado-Véliz, M., Jurado, F., & Vera, D. (2024). Environmental impact of the most representative Spanish olive oil farming systems: A life cycle assessment study. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 442, 141169.

- García-Velásquez, C., & Van der Meer, Y. (2023). Mind the Pulp: environmental and economic assessment of a sugar beet pulp biorefinery for biobased chemical production. *Waste Management*, 155, 199-210. 10.1016/j.wasman.2022.10.038
- Gargalo, C.L., Carvalho, A., Gernaey, K. V., Sin, G., 2016. A framework for techno-economic & environmental sustainability analysis by risk assessment for conceptual process evaluation. *Biochem. Eng. J.* 116, 146–156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bej.2016.06.007>
- Golaszewski, J., Morone, P., Majer, S., Razza, F., Ladu, L., Grill, M., Ugarte, S., Van Iersel, S., Voogt, M., Crepy, M., Fedrigo, D., Merloni, E., 2020. STAR-ProBio. Deliverable 8.2. Blueprint of sustainability certification schemes for bio-based products.
- Hagman, L., & Feiz, R. (2021). Advancing the circular economy through organic by-product valorisation: a multi-criteria assessment of a wheat-based biorefinery. *Waste and Biomass Valorization*, 12(11), 6205-6217. 10.1007/s12649-021-01440-y
- Hasenheit, M., Gerdes, H., Kiresiewa, Z., Beekman, V., 2016. Summary report on the social, economic and environmental impacts of the bioeconomy, Biostep.
- ILO, 1913. Information System on International Labour Standards, Normlex.
- Ioannidou, S. M., Filippi, K., Kookos, I. K., Koutinas, A., & Ladakis, D. (2022). Techno-economic evaluation and life cycle assessment of a biorefinery using winery waste streams for the production of succinic acid and value-added co-products. *Bioresource Technology*, 348, 126295. 10.1016/j.biortech.2021.126295
- Ioannidou, S. M., Ladakis, D., Moutousidi, E., Dheskali, E., Kookos, I. K., Câmara-Salim, I., ... & Koutinas, A. (2022). Techno-economic risk assessment, life cycle analysis and life cycle costing for poly (butylene succinate) and poly (lactic acid) production using renewable resources. *Science of The Total Environment*, 806, 150594. 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.150594
- Ioannidou, S. M., Stylianou, E., Pateraki, C., Kookos, I., Rabaey, K., Koutinas, A., & Ladakis, D. (2023). Techno-economic and environmental sustainability assessment of succinic acid production from municipal biowaste using an electrochemical membrane bioreactor. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 473, 145070.
- ISO, 2006. ISO 14040 Environmental Management - Life Cycle Assessment - Principles and Framework. Geneve.
- Jolliet, O., Antón, A., Boulay, A.-M., Cherubini, F., Fantke, P., Levasseur, A., McKone, T.E., Michelsen, O., Milà i Canals, L., Motoshita, M., Pfister, S., Verones, F., Vigon, B., Frischknecht, R., 2018. Global guidance on environmental life cycle impact assessment indicators: impacts of climate change, fine particulate matter formation, water consumption and land use. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 23, 2189–2207. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-018-1443-y>
- Kachrimanidou, V., Ioannidou, S. M., Ladakis, D., Papapostolou, H., Kopsahelis, N., Koutinas, A. A., & Kookos, I. K. (2021). Techno-economic evaluation and life-cycle assessment of poly (3-hydroxybutyrate) production within a biorefinery concept using sunflower-based biodiesel industry by-products. *Bioresource Technology*, 326, 124711. 10.1016/j.biortech.2021.124711

- Kim, H., Lee, S., Ahn, Y., Lee, J., & Won, W. (2020). Sustainable production of bioplastics from lignocellulosic biomass: techno-economic analysis and life-cycle assessment. *ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering*, 8(33), 12419-12429. [10.1021/acssuschemeng.0c02872](https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.0c02872)
- Kumar, R., Bhardwaj, A., Singh, L. P., & Singh, G. (2024). Environmental and economical assessment of maize cultivation in Northern India. *Process Integration and Optimization for Sustainability*, 8(1), 165-179. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41660-023-00358-3>
- Ladakis, D., Stylianou, E., Ioannidou, S. M., Koutinas, A., & Pateraki, C. (2022). Biorefinery development, techno-economic evaluation and environmental impact analysis for the conversion of the organic fraction of municipal solid waste into succinic acid and value-added fractions. *Bioresource Technology*, 354, 127172. [10.1016/j.biortech.2022.127172](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2022.127172)
- Ladu, L., Morone, P., 2021. Holistic approach in the evaluation of the sustainability of bio-based products: An Integrated Assessment Tool. *Sustain. Prod. Consum.* 28, 911-924e6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2021.07.006>
- Leire Iriarte, Fritsche, U.R., 2015a. D5.4. Consistent Cross-Sectoral Sustainability Criteria & Indicators. Final Report, S2BIOM.
- Leire Iriarte, Fritsche, U.R., 2015b. D5.4. Consistent Cross-Sectoral Sustainability Criteria & Indicators. Final Report, S2BIOM.
- Life Cycle Initiative, 2023. Our Mission, Vision and Approach [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.lifecycleinitiative.org/about/our-mission-vision-and-approach/> (accessed 5.5.23).
- Mahmud, R., Moni, S.M., High, K., Carbajales-Dale, M., 2021a. Integration of techno-economic analysis and life cycle assessment for sustainable process design – A review. *J. Clean. Prod.* 317, 128247. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.128247>
- Mahmud, R., Moni, S.M., High, K., Carbajales-Dale, M., 2021b. Integration of techno-economic analysis and life cycle assessment for sustainable process design – A review. *J. Clean. Prod.* 317, 128247. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.128247>
- Manfredi, S., Allacker, K., Chomkham Sri, K., Pelletier, N., Souza, D.M. de, 2012. Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) Guide, European Commission, Joint Research Centre, Institute for Environment and Sustainability.
- Marine Stewardship Council, 2023. MSC-MSCI Vocabulary.
- Matthias Stratmann, Sergio Ugarte, Kähler, F., Gulati, M., 2022. Study of the environmental sustainability requirements of biobased value chains and supply chains for bio-based industry in future EU funded R&I demonstration and flagship projects. Final report.
- Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2003. Ecosystems and Their Services, in: *Ecosystems and Human Well-Being: A Framework for Assessment*. Island Press, Washington, pp. 49–70.
- Mirzaei, M., Gorji Anari, M., Saronjic, N., Sarkar, S., Kral, I., Gronauer, A., ... & Caballero-Calvo, A. (2023). Environmental impacts of corn silage production: influence of

- wheat residues under contrasting tillage management types. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 195(1), 171. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-022-10675-8>
- Møller, H., Lyng, K. A., Røös, E., Samsonstuen, S., & Olsen, H. F. (2023). Circularity indicators and added value to traditional LCA impact categories: example of pig production. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-023-02150-4>
- Moutousidi, E. S., & Kookos, I. K. (2021). Life cycle assessment of biobased chemicals from different agricultural feedstocks. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 323, 129201. [10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.129201](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.129201)
- Müller-Wenk, R., & Brandão, M., 2010. Climatic impact of land use in LCA—carbon transfers between vegetation/soil and air. *Int J Life Cycle Assess*, 15, 172-182. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-009-0144-y>
- Ndue, K., Pál, G., 2022. Life Cycle Assessment Perspective for Sectoral Adaptation to Climate Change: Environmental Impact Assessment of Pig Production. *Land* 11, 827. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land11060827>
- Neugebauer, S., Forin, S., Finkbeiner, M., 2016. From Life Cycle Costing to Economic Life Cycle Assessment—Introducing an Economic Impact Pathway. *Sustainability* 8, 428. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su8050428>
- Norma Española (UNE), 2006. UNE-EN ISO 14040. Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Principles and framework.
- Norma Española (UNE), 2016. UNE-EN 16751. Bio-based products. Sustainability criteria.
- OECD, 2020a. The OECD Inventory of Circular Economy indicators.
- OECD, 2020b. The OECD Inventory of Circular Economy indicators.
- OECD, 2023. Material productivity [WWW Document]. OECD Data. URL <https://data.oecd.org/materials/material-productivity.htm> (accessed 12.13.22).
- Pan, S., Zabed, H. M., Zhao, M., Qi, X., & Wei, Y. (2023). Techno-economic and life cycle assessments for bioenergy recovery from acid-hydrolyzed residues of sugarcane bagasse in the biobased xylose production platform. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 400, 136718. [10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.136718](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.136718)
- Parliament, T.H.E.E., Council, T.H.E., The, O.F., Union, E., 2018. Directive 2014/24/EU of The European Parliament and of The Council of 26 February 2014 on public procurement and repealing Directive 2004/18/EC (Text with EEA relevance). Brussels Comment. *EU Public Procure. Law* 2014, 65–242. <https://doi.org/10.5040/9781509923205.0008>
- Peters, M.S., Timmerhaus, K.D., West, R.E., 2003. *Plant design and economics for chemical engineers*, 5th ed. McGraw-Hill Professional.
- Rajendran, N., Runge, T., Bergman, R. D., Nepal, P., & Houtman, C. (2023). Techno-economic analysis and life cycle assessment of cellulose nanocrystals production from wood pulp. *Bioresource Technology*, 377, 128955. [10.1016/j.biortech.2023.128955](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2023.128955)

- Razza, F., Briani, C., Breton, T., & Marazza, D. (2020). Metrics for quantifying the circularity of bioplastics: The case of bio-based and biodegradable mulch films. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 159, 104753. [10.1016/j.resconrec.2020.104753](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2020.104753)
- Rebolledo-Leiva, R., Moreira, M.T., González-García, S., 2023. Progress of social assessment in the framework of bioeconomy under a life cycle perspective. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 175, 113162. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2023.113162>
- Reyntjens, D., Brown, J., 2005. INDECO. Indicators: An Overview.
- Rugani, B., Osset, P., Blanc, O., Benetto, E., 2023. Environmental Footprint Neutrality Using Methods and Tools for Natural Capital Accounting in Life Cycle Assessment. *Land* 12, 1171. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land12061171>
- Saad, R., Koellner, T., & Margni, M., 2013. Land use impacts on freshwater regulation, erosion regulation, and water purification: a spatial approach for a global scale level. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 18, 1253-1264. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-013-0577-1>
- Sahoo, K., Upadhyay, A., Runge, T., Bergman, R., Puettmann, M., & Bilek, E. (2021). Life-cycle assessment and techno-economic analysis of biochar produced from forest residues using portable systems. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 26, 189-213. [10.1007/s11367-020-01830-9](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-020-01830-9)
- Sala, S., Amadei, A.M., Beylot, A., Ardente, F., 2021. The evolution of life cycle assessment in European policies over three decades. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 26, 2295–2314. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-021-01893-2>
- Sala, S., Vasta, A., Lucia Mancini, Jo Dewulf, E.R., 2015. Social Life Cycle Assessment - State of the art and challenges for supporting product policies, in: *Materials and Sustainable Development*. European Commission, Joint Research Centre, Institute for Environment and Sustainability, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxemburg, pp. 1–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-98361-7.00006-3>
- Seghetta, M., Hou, X., Bastianoni, S., Bjerre, A. B., & Thomsen, M. (2016). Life cycle assessment of macroalgal biorefinery for the production of ethanol, proteins and fertilizers—a step towards a regenerative bioeconomy. *Journal of Cleaner production*, 137, 1158-1169. [10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.07.195](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.07.195)
- Sonderegger, T., Dewulf, J., Fantke, P., de Souza, D.M., Pfister, S., Stoessel, F., Verones, F., Vieira, M., Weidema, B., Hellweg, S., 2017. Towards harmonizing natural resources as an area of protection in life cycle impact assessment. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 22, 1912–1927. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-017-1297-8>
- Swedish University of Agricultural Science, 2023. Difficult to reach consensus on how climate-smart it is to manage forests [WWW Document]. SLU's Knowl. bank. URL <https://www.slu.se/en/research/knowledge-bank/2023/difficult-to-reach-consensus-on-how-climate-smart-it-is-to-manage-forests/> (accessed 5.4.23).
- Turton, R., Shaeiwitz, J.A., Bhattacharyya, D., Whiting, W.B., 2018. *Analysis, Synthesis, and Design of Chemical Processes*. Prentice Hall, New Jersey.
- UNE, 2016. UNE-EN 16751. Bio-based products-Sustainability criteria.

- UNEP Life Cycle Initiative, Social LC Alliance, 2020. Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Organizations 2020, United Nations Environment Programme (unepe).
- UNEP-SETAC Life Cycle Initiative, 2019a. Global Guidance on Environmental Life Cycle Impact Assessment Indicators. Volume 1.
- UNEP-SETAC Life Cycle Initiative, 2019b. Global Guidance on Environmental Life Cycle Impact Assessment Indicators. Volume 2.
- UNEP-SETAC Life Cycle Initiative, 2023. Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment [WWW Document]. Life Cycle Sustain. Assess.
- UNI, 2022. UNI/PdR 135:2022. Bio-based products - Organization and product application guidelines for environmental and social qualification.
- United Nations, 2023. What is renewable energy? [WWW Document]. Clim. action. URL <https://www.un.org/en/climatechange/what-is-renewable-energy> (accessed 4.21.23).
- Varavallo, G., Rugani, B., Allocco, M., Barbera, F., & Calfapietra, C. Tree-based model for achieving environmental impact neutrality: A case study application in the agri-food sector. Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.2879>
- Vidal-Legaz, B., Sala, S., Antón, A., Souza, D.M. De, Nocita, M., Putman, B., Teixeira, R.F.M., 2016. Land-use related environmental indicators for life cycle assessment - Analysis of key aspects in land use modelling - Study. <https://doi.org/10.2788/905478>
- Vinci, G., Prencipe, S. A., Ruggeri, M., Gobbi, L., & Arcese, G. (2024). Sustainability performance evaluation in the organic durum wheat production: evidence from Italy. The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment, 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-024-02302-0>
- Vis, M., Mantau, U., Allen, B., 2016. CASCADES-Study on the optimised cascading use of wood. No 394/PP/ENT/RCH/14/7689. Final report. Brussels.
- Zuorro, A., García-Martínez, J. B., Barajas-Solano, A. F., Rodríguez-Lizcano, A., & Kafarov, V. (2023). Environmental Footprint of Inland Fisheries: Integrating LCA Analysis to Assess the Potential of Wastewater-Based Microalga Cultivation as a Promising Solution for Animal Feed Production. Processes, 11(11), 3255. 10.3390/pr11113255

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